

MISSIONE 4
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Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

Education
& Lifelong Learning

i NEST

Milestone #26

Report

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1. Introduction

Economic, health and geopolitical trends have created globally in 2023 divergent outcomes for labour markets as widely reported in the “Future of Jobs” 2023 Report of World Economic Forum and in related reports [1-8], and shortly described in Figures 1-2.

Some of the key-issues associated to technological innovations can be summarized as follows:

- technology adoption will remain a key driver of business transformation in the next five years. Within the further development of technology, it is likely that big data, cybersecurity, cloud computing and AI will be more and more adopted;
- the impact of most technologies on jobs is expected to be positive over the next five years, but employers anticipate a structural labour market churn of 23% of jobs in the next five years;
- the human-machine frontier has shifted, with businesses introducing automation into their operations at a slower pace than previously anticipated.

The combination of macro-trends and technology adoption will drive specific areas of job growth and decline:

- the fastest-growing roles relative to their actual size are driven by technology, digitalization and sustainability;
- the fastest-declining roles relative to their actual size are driven by technology and digitalization;
- a large-scale job growth is expected in the sectors of education, agriculture and digital commerce and trade;
- the largest losses of job are expected in administrative roles and in traditional security, factory and commerce roles;
- analytical thinking and creative thinking remain the most important skills for workers still in 2023.

As a consequence of this scenario, employers estimate that 44% of workers’ skills will be disrupted in the next five years. In other words, 6 out of 10 workers will require massive reskilling and training before 2027, although only half of workers are seen to have access to adequate training opportunities today.

The skills that companies consider increasingly important are not always reflected in corporate upskilling strategies. Even if employers express confidence in developing their existing workforce, they display less optimism when outlook the talents’ availability in the next five years.

Investing in learning and on-the-job training and automating processes are the most common workforce strategies which will be adopted to deliver organizations’ business goals.

As part of their DEI (Diversity, Equity and Inclusion) programmes, the majority of companies will prioritize:

- women (79%),
- youth under 25 (68%),
- and those with disabilities (51%)

45% of businesses see funding for skills training as a government intervention able to connect talent to employment.

Starting from this scenario, the objectives of the cross-cutting action “Education & Lifelong Learning” within the iNEST project and in territorial context of the Ecosystem will be focused on the development of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that enable people to contribute to and benefit from an inclusive and sustainable future. Such process will be based on two pillars:

- Education, to equip students with the capabilities they need to thrive and become active, responsible and engaged citizens,
- Lifelong Learning, which is strategic to bolster innovation within society, and in particular into SMEs.

Figure 1 – Expected impact of technology adoption on jobs, 2023–2027

Figure 2 – Projected job creation and displacement

The state of the art developed in the frame of Milestone #25 of iNEST project [9] evidenced that the effort of iNEST Partner Universities in education and lifelong learning is strong, highly motivated and with relevant attention to innovation. In that report, some challenges have been identified:

- developing the capability, in perfect agreement with the mission of iNEST Ecosystem, of sharing, improving, upgrading these excellent experiences among universities,
- making such experiences and tools available not only to own students, but also to students still in high schools,
- opening new up-skilling scenarios for those already involved in professional activities and jobs,
- contributing to exploiting of Nord-Est potential by realizing a systemic vision of the overall Education path of persons.

iNEST is trying to develop, as an ecosystem, an overall and integrated vision of educational path of people, starting from high school and coming up to lifelong learning during professional life (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Overall and integrated vision of Education path of persons

Under these premises, the key-areas identified for action at the ecosystem level are:

- **Guidance, Counselling and Tutoring**
- **Education paths, tools and methodologies**
- **Inter- e trans-disciplinary initiatives**
- **Lifelong learning**

This document reviews the actions designed for being performed in the frame of these key areas.

2. Guidance, Counselling and Tutoring

For the students' successful completion of study courses, universities are required to undertake study orientation activities and tutoring activities. The decline in the number of secondary school graduates enrolling into tertiary studies, the high drop-out rate and the difficulty of completing a university course are issues that can be overcome by supporting young people in choosing the right study program and during the first years of their university studies. At national level, as well as in the frame of PNRR programme, a strong focus is given to these kinds of activities, which are strategic to increase the efficiency of the overall learning system.

The most relevant programmes that have been financed are shortly described below.

The National Plan for Science degrees (PLS)

Launched by MUR, the National Plan for Science Degrees (PLS) aims at stimulating the students' interest in science, and offers training courses for teachers. It also favours interaction between university and businesses to facilitate student's entry into the high-tech job world. PLS typically offers upper secondary school students and teachers the following services:

- workshops
- conferences
- internships
- courses and seminars
- visits to research laboratories
- science theatre and cinema

Orientation and Tutoring Programmes (POT)

To support universities in this area, MUR has activated calls for Tutoring and Orientation Programmes (POT), in coordination with the previously mentioned PLS initiatives. POT aims at encouraging universities to integrate their development strategies with orientation and education success plans for all degree courses. In the last two years, orientation courses have been organized at the upper secondary level as well as in the period between school graduation and university enrolment (thus in collaboration with high schools); they can include:

- workshops for skill identification and personal development, with a focus on the selection of suitable university studies and job opportunities;
- meetings between schoolteachers and university instructors to develop guidance for the development of orientation strategies;
- designing student self-assessment tests.

The above list shows a focus on the "knowledge of professional sectors and their connection with university education". The tutoring activities are targeted to students enrolled in the first or second year of a Bachelor's, Master's, or single-cycle Master's Degree programme, in particular those experiencing challenges to adapt; such activities can include:

- training initiatives for student tutors to provide the basic tools needed to support and guide students;
- support material for tutoring activities, which can also be used in subsequent years, to consolidate good practices;
- monitoring actions to identify the most effective tutoring methods materials, and procedures.

iNEST Universities are highly involved in PLS and POT initiatives, as reported in Table 1 [10-11], showing the list of recently (August 2023) approved PLS/POT programmes running from 2023 to 2025. The yellow background displays the projects related to iNEST and its Spokes thematic areas.

Type	Coordinator	Title	U N I T N	U N I U D	I U A V	U N I P D	U N I V E	U N I V R	U N I T S
PLS	UNIBO	Progetto Nazionale Geologia				✓			✓
PLS	UNICT	Progetto Nazionale di Biologia e Biotecnologie	✓	✓				✓	✓
PLS	UNIMI	Progetto Nazionale di INFORMATICA		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
PLS	UNIMIB	Progetto Nazionale Chimica				✓			✓
PLS	UNIMIB	Progetto Nazionale LS di Scienza dei Materiali							✓
PLS	UNIPA	Progetto Nazionale di Statistica				✓			✓
PLS	UNIPA	Progetto Nazionale di FISICA	✓			✓		✓	✓
PLS	UNIPI	Progetto nazionale di Matematica		✓		✓		✓	✓
PLS	UNIVPM	PLS in Scienze Naturali e Ambientali				✓	✓		✓
POT	UNICAMPANIA	PROMETHEUS 2.0				✓		✓	
POT	UNIPI	UniSco - Azioni Università-Scuola per competenze in lingue, letterature, mediazione linguistica				✓			✓
POT	UNIROMA1	MedOdontOrientaDomain-MOOD				✓		✓	✓
POT	IUAV	POT_Architettura		✓	✓				✓
POT	UNIROMA1	SUL - Scuola e Università per Lettere				✓	✓	✓	
POT	UNISALENTO	Scienze delle Attività Motorie e Sportive				✓		✓	
POT	UNINA	INGEGNERIA.POT	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
POT	UNISI	Verso. Sistemi di orientamento e tutorato per le professioni educative e formative		✓		✓		✓	✓
POT	UNISA	Geolocalizzazione Politico-Sociologica per orientarsi nel mondo UNiversitario				✓		✓	✓
POT	UNIMOL	SISSA3EFG - Sistema Integrato Studenti Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari, Animali, Enologiche, Forestali, Gastronomiche		✓		✓		✓	
POT	UNISALENTO	C.A.R.E: Orientamento e formazione professione insegnante		✓		✓		✓	
POT	UNIROMA3	Università, scuole e territorio in rete per il patrimonio culturale materiale e immateriale		✓		✓	✓	✓	
POT	UNIPV	V.A.L.E. - P.L.U.S. (Vocational Academic Law Enhancement - Project Law University Student)	✓			✓		✓	✓
POT	UNIPD	Orientare ed Orientarsi tra le Scienze del Farmaco				✓			✓
POT	UNIMI	Tutorato Orientamento Professioni Sanitarie - TOP		✓		✓		✓	
POT	UNITUS	IN DIALOGO CON IL RESTAURO							
POT	UNINA	ServizioSociale.Pot				✓		✓	✓
POT	UNICAMPANIA	NEED_new empathic educational design							
POT	UNITO	TALENTI - ECONOMIA, MANAGEMENT E TURISMO		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
POT	UNIME	OrientaVET: orientamento-tutorato per lo studente				✓			

Table 1 – Recently (August 2023) approved PLS/POT programmes [10-11]

Furthermore, in the frame of PNRR (section called “Orientamento attivo nella transizione scuola università”/ active guidance in the school to university transition), several initiatives are being planned and some are already ongoing in Italian Universities, such as guidance courses” addressed to students finishing high school. The goal is to support the young generation of a knowledge-based society by improving knowledge about higher education paths, experiential learning, as well as developing: a scientific approach to learning, the availability of self-evaluation tools, transversal competences and employability skills, knowledge on work environments.

As a consequence of these relevant and highly motivated effort and funding addressed to guidance, counselling and tutoring, iNEST activities will be directed to coordination and sharing of initiatives and experiences. Only a specific Forum, aimed at comparing pilot projects about guidance to convert students’ drop-out into a new and successful career, will be organised.

3. Educational paths, tools and methodologies

The iNEST Education – State of the Art document [9] evidenced the activities performed by Nord-Est Universities to develop innovative pedagogies, tools and methodologies for innovative and efficient learning processes.

In this context, it is worth –mentioning:

- Innovative teaching workshops (Active Learning Lab, Design Thinking, Business Modelling, Social research, Storytelling and Public Speaking)
- Team-based learning (TBL) experiences
- Group working in large classes
- Innovative tutoring (and training to tutoring) initiatives
- Initiatives to support gender equality especially in STEM disciplines:
 - Equal opportunities and inclusion initiatives
 - Courses on gender balance, in cooperation with local Institutions
 - Awards to highlight the role of women in STEM disciplines
 - Gender equality initiatives (Women in Maths and Women in Physics to reverse imbalance in gender representation at academic & research levels in mathematics and physics)
- Development of learners and teachers' communities
 - Learning Factory (Smart Mini Factory)
 - Communities of Practice
 - Contamination Lab Verona – Clab Verona
 - Competency Center
 - Teaching4Learning permanent Working Group and periodic Conference
 - Participation to European alliance with a focus on innovative teaching
- Set up of innovative hardware system for video-lessons, characterised by high interactivity and supporting increased learning efficiency,
- Pilot project for virtualization of ICT labs and of technological labs,
- Internal calls supporting innovative training initiatives

Annex 1 collects the shared proposals of iNEST's education partners addressed at developing initiatives, pilot-projects, tools and methodologies to support advanced and efficient learning processes. A shared use and a survey across users of these solutions and initiatives will help iNESt Ecosystem develop methodological and strategic approaches, incorporating the contribution of different teams and persons.

Facing new educational challenges needs open mind approaches, upscaling learning productivity by means of innovative use of novel digital tools and media. iNEST will contribute to this target through collaborative endeavours in which teacher and learners manage together their respective improvement.

4. Inter- e trans-disciplinary initiatives

Companies devote big efforts to understand key-skills for workers and to improve training activities and ultimately the employees’ potential in these key areas. Figure 6, for instance, reviews the most important skills of the workforce, according to company managers. The figure highlights not only the strategic role of creativity thinking and analytical thinking, but also their increasing importance (Figure 7). Also technology literacy is becoming increasingly relevant; in terms of attitudes, “curiosity and lifelong learning” and “resilience, flexibility and agility” are becoming key in the next years. All in all, we are entering a scenario of continuously evolving skills landscape (Figure 8), with the need of addressing the workforce’s reskilling and upskilling in the next five years.

Figure 6 – Share of surveyed organizations considering certain skills to be core for their workforce. Estimated average composition of the skill sets of workers in the organizations surveyed. Skills are ranked and ordered by the share of organizations surveyed considering the skill as core for their workforce

Figure 7 – Share of organizations surveyed who consider skills to be of increasing or decreasing importance, ranked by the net difference.

From these surveys, it is clear the need of a lifelong learning approach based not only on disciplinary content (with a focus on technological areas), but also based on the nurturing of analytical and critical thinking skills. This need has been already intercepted by iNEST Universities, as highlighted in the Education Working Group report published in March 2023. Furthermore, iNEST Project provides also the opportunity of sharing, coordinating and improving inter-disciplinary approaches, leading learners to an improved vision and attitude to problem solving and a sensibility towards interdisciplinary and lifelong learning.

To do this, [Annex 2](#) to this document collects the shared proposals of iNEST’s alliance in education addressed at making available, on an Ecosystem scale:

- **Minors subjects.** They offer the perfect opportunity to enrich students’ master's degree with supplemental competences, that is knowledge, skills and attitudes appropriate to the context. They typically consist of 3-4 courses which are generally related to the main study program, and are chosen by learners to develop complementary and cross-cutting, as well as specializing, competencies. In this way, students seek to make themselves more attractive to employers. To make an example, it is common for students majoring in physics to minor in computer science, or for a learner in engineering or economics to minor in mathematics or informatics, or even sustainability-related disciplines.

- **Challenges and Hackathons.** These are designed to develop fast-paced transversal skills, such as innovation, dynamism, and quick problem-solving. These events allow research students to use strategies like Design-based Thinking through Challenge-Based Learning (CBL). An example of one such event is a hackathon. A hackathon is a rapid, time-bound, and compact event where participants must find a solution to a problem. In hackathons people gather to think and generate technological innovations. These events are taking place worldwide and are often promoted by organizations that look outside their boundaries to search for innovation and, in so doing, improve their business. This framework empowers learners (students, teachers, administrators and community members) to address local and global challenges while acquiring cross cutting knowledge in math, science, social studies, language arts, medicine, technology, engineering, computer science and the arts as well. Through Challenge Based Learning, students and teachers are making a difference to develop deep learning that is engaging, meaningful, and purposeful; they also develop a life-long learning attitude. Because these events bring together multidisciplinary teams, they provide participants with the opportunities to: (i) encourage creative and collective hinking, leading to new and innovative concepts, ideas, and prototypes; and (ii) expand their network with potential future cooperations.
- **Erasmus INEST.** It has been recently approved the “Italian Erasmus” project (published on the Gazzetta Ufficiale, 27/07/2023), aimed at improving students’ mobility between Italian universities, and consequently to further support the genesis of multi- and inter-disciplinary professional profiles. The upgrading of Regulations and Legislation will be finalized by MUR in the coming months (the deadline being 30 November 2023). Some pilot agreements have already been signed and applied by the Universities cooperating in the iNEST project, for example between IUAV and the Ca’ Foscari University of Venice, or by UNIBZ and other universities in Italy). This opportunity will be further explored and pursued by the iNEST university partners.

Figure 8 – The evolving skills landscape, 2023-2027 – The probability of an organization surveyed evaluating a skill to be a core skill for its workers in 2023 versus the probability of the skill appearing in its reskilling and upskilling initiative in the next five years

As a more general remark, it has to be considered that society in its broader meaning is improved not only by entrepreneurs but also by individuals with entrepreneurship competence (set of knowledge, attitudes and skills for opportunity recognition and exploitation, value creation, and action orientation; EntreComp). Such individuals are more prone to identify problems and take actions, enhancing social as well as economic well-being. Entrepreneurship Education (EE) is seen as a major driving force to enhance the development of entrepreneurship competence” [12-13].

Some of the iNEST developed initiatives will address these issues, too.

5. Lifelong learning

The literature acknowledges the increasingly important role of continuous training during the career as well the growing role of lifelong learning. Lifelong learning can be defined as the ongoing, voluntary, and self-motivated pursuit of knowledge through lifespan and including non-formal and informal environments (sport clubs, associations, ...) for either personal or professional reasons. While it is important for an individual's competitiveness and employability, it also enhances social inclusion, active citizenship, and personal development. Lifelong learning will be performed adopting different approaches and strategies, as shown in Figures 9 and 10, depending on size and characteristics of companies.

Figure 9 – Training provision, 2023-2027: The expected mean composition of training programmes

Figure 10 – Upskilling and reskilling outlook, 2023-2027, by workforce fraction – A breakdown of the average training strategy for a representative group of 100 employees, calculated based on the training strategies reported by organizations surveyed

A specific investigation carried out recently by the School of Engineering of Padova University, involving around 50 social parties, with representatives of industrial associations, innovative regional networks, professional engineers boards and relevant companies and companies associations, highlighted the general requirements on the needs, targets, topics and modalities of the impacting lifelong learning initiatives, with a potential audience of several hundreds of companies and thousands of employees.

- a) Participants' profile. Lifelong learning programs are needed by all profiles involved in industrial and professional activities (Figure 11): undergraduates with several years of experience in the companies, senior graduated engineers, managers and also recently graduated engineers.
- b) Optimal weekly effort for lifelong learning modules. Training effort must be related to the employees' working effort: in most cases (62%, Figure 12) a work-load (for lectures) of 4 hours a week of lifelong learning activities (courses, workshops, lectures, self reflection and self-paced activities) is considered a sustainable effort, also thanks to the flexibility associated to the availability of on-line training tools (such as synchronous and asynchronous courses , including MOOCs).
- c) Ongoing periodic formative assessment. Training activities, even in basically performed on-line with an a-synchronous approach, can be made more efficient by scheduling periodic (synchronous) meetings with teachers (62%, Figure 13) to receive and give formative feedback.
- d) How relevant is the formal certification of Lifelong Learning. Quality of Lifelong Learning modules is assured also by a formal and self-consistent digital certification process: this is the opinion expressed by 76% of answers (Figure 14).

Figure 11 – Target participants for Lifelong Learning Courses

Figure 12 – Optimal weekly effort to attend the Lifelong Learning courses

Figure 13 – Relevance of a periodic assessment with a board of teachers

Figure 14 – Relevance of formal certification of knowledge achieved

Thus, a structured and adequate Lifelong Learning programme fully coherent with the framework of iNEST should take into account:

- Training programmes aligned with the main topics characterizing each Spoke,
- Structure of courses based on flexibility and blended approaches, with on-line synchronous and asynchronous MOOCs integrated with meetings with the board of teachers,
- Involvement of teachers and trainers with different backgrounds, both in terms of technical profiles and of professional experience (companies, universities, consultancy services) ,
- Development of a self-developed certification system, based on micro-credential approach.

Annex 3 collects a preliminary catalogue of the lifelong learning initiatives which will be shared among the universities of the iNEST ecosystem.

6. iNEST Plan for Education and Lifelong Learning

iNEST elaborated a comprehensive for Education and Lifelong Learning initiatives in the Ecosystem. They can be summarized as follows:

- **Guidance, Counselling and Tutoring:** organization of a POT-PLS Forum to share best practices and start the design of drop-out recovering pilot-projects;
- **Education paths, tools and methodologies:** 15 initiatives, pilot-projects, tools and methodologies to support advanced and efficient learning processes, as shown in Fig. 16 and detailed in Annex 1;
- **Inter- e trans-disciplinary initiatives:** 19 Minors, Challenges and Hackatons addressed to students of iNEST Partner Universities, as shown in Fig. 17 and detailed in Annex 2;
- **Lifelong learning: 26 Lifelong Learning initiatives,** as shown in Fig. 18 and detailed in Annex 3.

Figure 16 – iNEST Plan about initiatives, pilot-projects, tools and methodologies to support advanced and efficient learning processes

Figure 17 – iNEST Plan about Minors, Challenges and Hackatons

Figure 18 – iNEST Plan about Lifelong Learning initiatives

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Milestone #26

Annex 1

*Innovative
Education
Initiatives
& Pilot-
Projects
Catalogue*

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Persons	Margherita Molinaro, Erwin Rauch
Key-descriptors	
Title	Special track on “Innovative Engineering Education” at the 3rd ISIEA Conference
TAGS	#Innovative Education #Engineering #Learning Factories
Duration	Half day
Details	
Background	The <i>International Symposium on Industrial Engineering and Automation</i> (ISIEA) has been launched in 2022 as a new initiative of the Industrial Engineering and Automation macro-area of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. It is an international scientific conference (with proceedings published in September as a volume of Springer’s Lecture Notes) dealing with different Engineering topics. The topic of the 2024 edition will be Latest Advancements In Mechanical Engineering. We plan to organize a new special track within the conference focused on “Innovative Engineering Education”.
Description of initiative/project	A special track/session will be organized within the 3 rd ISIEA Conference dealing with tools, methods, and formats for Engineering Education. This will offer a platform also to iNEST staff to exchange best practices and experiences to strengthen the higher education teaching offer in the Engineering field. Examples of topics that will be included in the track are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New (digital) tools for Engineering Educations; - The role of Learning Factories in Engineering Education; - Serious Games for Engineering Education; - Problem-Based Learning in Engineering Education; - Engineering Curricula Design; - Integrating Digitalization and Sustainability in Engineering Education; - Life-Long Learning in the Engineering field.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	iNEST professors and researchers (in particular in the Engineering field) belonging to all the Spokes will be invited to present a paper or attend the special track on Innovative Engineering Education.
References	Conference website (under construction): https://isiea.events.unibz.it/
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	All professors and researchers interested in the topic can submit a paper and attend the track (paying the registration fee for the conference that will cover the organization costs, i.e., website, catering, etc.).

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Roberta Cuel
Key-descriptors	
Title	Theatrical Improvisation Workshop for high school teachers
TAGS	Extract keywords by the project: Theatrical improvisation, Team building, Trust in teams, Listening Acceptance of the proposal, Lateral thinking, Communication management
Duration	The laboratory consists of 4 lessons of 3 hours, for 12 hours. We plan to conduct this activity in different high schools and university courses for three years.
Details	
Background	Improvisation is a theatrical technique that encourages participants to react collaboratively by adopting creative strategies to adapt to stimuli and seek solutions to problems that arise.
Description of initiative/project	The course encourages acquiring skills and tools for group work, negotiation, and team collaboration. Theatrical improvisation is very effective for developing a range of basic emotional, relational, and cognitive skills that allow people to acquire versatile and positive behavior helpful in working in groups, such as being able to listen empathically to other members of the group, promote creative and adaptive capacity in solving problems, learn to accept the proposal and think divergently, improve the management of individual decisions, increase the ability to stay focused on objectives and acquire tools for conflict management. From a social point of view, collaboration skills are developed, social stereotypes are eliminated, and awareness of the value of each individual in their peculiarities is created. Consequently, acceptance and integration are achieved among all class group members.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The lessons are divided into two parts. The first part includes exercises focused on bodily expressiveness, movement, facial and vocal expressiveness, and group dynamics. The second part focuses on verbal expressiveness and allows participants to experiment with jokes and practice their expressive potential in a welcoming environment that encourages creativity and emotional expression. The proposed exercises promote body awareness, emotional awareness, and active listening to others. Lesson 1: Public speaking and effective communication. - This initial journey focuses on bodily expressiveness and vocal techniques to develop effective communication and public speaking skills. The goal is to create a trusting and dynamic group environment where everyone can feel comfortable expressing themselves creatively. Lesson 2: Improvisation tools as resources for teachers. - This part of the lessons offers improvisation tools that can be used as resources for teachers to manage eye contact, active listening, and creativity in finding innovative solutions. Lesson 3: The relationship between the education and education sector. - Theoretical studies on knowledge sharing, group management, confrontation, and conflict management are explored to deepen the understanding of the relationship between education and the education sector. Through theories and experiential exercises, the theme of the effects of improvisation in work groups (such as class councils) and the management of confrontation and conflict between colleagues will be explored. Lesson 4: Dealing with others. -This final part of the lessons includes a series of exercises to put the tools learned in previous meetings into practice and to effectively approach relationships. Alongside the technical-expressive methodologies, reflection-sharing methodologies are also used to help participants reflect on the challenges of communicating clearly and personally while understanding the importance of welcoming listening.
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Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	<i>The course will initially be aimed at high school teachers and students of some university courses; then, it will be extended to other schools that request it.</i>

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Paola Venuti, Anna Serbati
Key-descriptors	
Title	Students' wellbeing and inclusive education at university
TAGS	Students' wellbeing, inclusion, prevention, higher education
Duration	8h
Details	
Background	To our knowledge, most of the research on university students' health has focused on examining the prevalence of distress and on the student's use of support services when experiencing mental health difficulties. However, less research has focused on preventive measures that universities could take to reduce environmental stressors and promote students' well-being in the university environment.
Description of initiative/project	The seminar builds on the potential of innovative and creative teaching methods for enhancing teaching quality that could improve students' well-being. It responds to the priority to develop academic teaching skills and methods that protect students' mental health. In fact, the seminar focuses on preventive measures of students' well-being and strategies to create an inclusive learning environment. Case studies and methodologies will be analyzed and discussed; participants will design a draft of teaching activity including participatory approaches based on universal design for learning and focusing on students' emotions.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Students' well-being, teaching and learning methods for inclusion, assessment methods for inclusion
References	Burgstahler, S. (2020). <i>Creating inclusive learning opportunities in higher education: A universal design toolkit</i> (pp. 47-48). Cambridge, MA: Harvard Education Press. Larcombe, W., Finch, S., Sore, R., Murray, C. M., Kentish, S., Mulder, R. A., ... & Williams, D. A. (2016). Prevalence and socio-demographic correlates of psychological distress among students at an Australian university. <i>Studies in higher education</i> , 41(6), 1074-1091. Oleson, K. C. (2023). <i>Promoting inclusive classroom dynamics in higher education: A research-based pedagogical guide for faculty</i> . Taylor & Francis.
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	The seminar is devoted to all academics and students' representatives

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Paola Venuti, Anna Serbati
Key-descriptors	
Title	Educational leadership at university
TAGS	Educational leadership, management, teaching and learning innovation, quality assurance
Duration	12h + 16h
Details	
Background	<p>As the international literature underlines (Bolander Laksov, 2017;2021) middle-management staff, delegates, and department heads are crucial to promote the success of developmental programs for the innovation of teaching, learning and assessment processes in University.</p> <p>As a result, it becomes important for institutional leaders to participate in advanced training courses that will enable them to contribute to the development of a high-quality learning and assessment environment in their context</p>
Description of initiative/project	<p>Starting from the literature evidence, two seminars devoted to course coordinators and teaching delegates will be organised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two days workshop for course coordinators: this initiative will include an introductory theoretical part dedicated to the topic of educational leadership with experts on the subject: reflective activities will be proposed through group work based on the cooperative learning technique. Specifically, the first part of the workshop will address the national regulatory directions and the duties of course coordinators in the framework of AVA3 standards. The second part will focus on active and innovative teaching and learning methodologies, also in connection with the specificity of their educational leadership role as course coordinators • Two days workshop for teaching delegates: this initiative will include an introductory theoretical part dedicated to the topic of educational leadership with experts on the subject. Participants will be invited to develop a personal structured reflection on their practice (with the adoption of specific tools), starting from a problematic issue related to their practice or specific tasks connected to their role. After the individual reflection, teaching delegates will be invited to discuss their experiences in pairs/groups and then with the class groups. An important part of this program will be based on the power of sharing practices connected to the teaching delegates activities in their departments. During the two days workshop, teaching delegates will be able to understand and reflect on specific techniques, such as reflective team and mentoring approach, to be exported and adopted in their departments
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Educational leadership, middle-management competences, formative path to sustain leadership skills for academics in Higher Education.
References	<p>Adams, D., Kutty, G. R., & Zabidi, Z. M. (2017). Educational leadership for the 21st century. <i>International online Journal of educational leadership</i>, 1(1), 1-4.</p> <p>Bolander Laksov, K. (2021). <i>In partnership with heads of department for sustainable educational development</i>. <i>International Journal for Academic Development</i>, 26(2), 136-147. https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2021.2016414</p> <p>Bolander Laksov, K., & Tomson, T. (2017). <i>Becoming an educational leader – exploring leadership in medical education</i>. <i>International Journal of Leadership in Education</i>, 20(4), 506-516. https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2015.1114152</p> <p>Bush, T., Middlewood, D., & Bell, L. (2019). Principles of educational leadership & management. <i>Principles of Educational Leadership & Management</i>, 1-408.</p>
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	The seminars are devoted to departmental teaching delegates and course coordinators

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Wooden construction Live Workshop
TAGS	Workshop, practical experience, wood, Venice
Duration	40 hours in total, 20 hours lectures and 20 hours practical activities with teachers
Details	
Background	The workshop is aimed at students of master's degree courses. Preliminary skills in architectural technology are required
Description of initiative/project	<p>The proposed course is configured as an experimental method of teaching in architecture in which the notions learned in frontal lectures are subsequently enhanced in practical experience.</p> <p>The main area of reference is wooden constructions.</p> <p>The objective of the workshop is to provide students with technical skills on wooden constructions that include both compositional and construction principles.</p> <p>The aim is to train future architects who know how to consciously design wooden structures, being able to appropriately exploit the potential of the material, especially in relation to its environmental sustainability.</p> <p>The structure of the workshop is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A first part where students will follow ex-cathedra lectures at university; - A second part where student will design a wooden structure; - A third part where students will construct, with the support of a company, the design structure. <p>The object of the workshop is the design of docking structures and/or information pavilions on the Certosa island in Venice.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The workshop focuses on sustainability in the construction sector. The practical experience is localized in the city of Venice that is the main pilot of the iNest Spoke 4. Innovative solutions and materials will be tested in the practical experience.
References	Oppenheimer, Andrea; Hursley, Timothy (2002). <i>Rural Studio: Samuel Mockbee and the Architecture of Decency</i> . Princeton Architectural Press. http://ruralstudio.org
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	<i>Reserved to Iuav Students</i>

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Stefano Ghidoni
Key-descriptors	
Title	Virtualization of Laboratories: The T.2020 Project
TAGS	ICT Lab, Virtual labs, BYOD
Duration	
Details	
Background	<p>The study of engineering – but also of the history of art or digital humanities – increasingly requires to be able to use multimedia tools for simulation even during lessons. The system allows the teacher to start multimedia laboratory activities in each classroom of the University, without having to book traditional resources (such as the IT classrooms of the various departments), which are now insufficient for the needs of the teachings, that use computing devices.</p> <p>T.2020 introduces the Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) approach, in which students can use their own devices to connect to the scientific software installed on the IT Services servers of the University.</p> <p>The project provides training for teachers (teaching for learning), who must be prepared for the change in the didactic paradigm.</p>
Description of initiative/project	<p>The T.2020 System, as the result of the work of a special commission of the School of Engineering formed in 2017, includes a systemic “vision” on IT services for teaching aimed at creating a perfect match between the needs of teachers and the tools available of the students.</p> <p>The study considered the IT tools for teaching – digital learning – (initially for Engineering teaching) and set the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • classrooms designed for teaching that combines the traditional frontal method in the classroom with activities mediated by computers or mobile systems (teaching blended), including modalities in which (1) the lesson becomes homework, while the time in the classroom is used for collaborative activities , experiences, debates and workshops (Flipped Classroom) and (2) active learning moments are incorporated to make training more engaging and akin to the needs of future professionals (Active Learning); • didactic structures that adopt criteria to facilitate inclusion , in order to favor the improvement of university life of all female students and all students and to reduce drop-out; • tools aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the teaching action, in relation to the number of students / year expected.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Seminars on the T.2020 system will be organized by the T.2020 Commission of the School of Engineering of Padova University. Pilot sessions for professors and students of iNEST Universities will be made available.
References	https://vlab.unipd.it/en/home-english/
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	No specific requirements

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Marina De Rossi
Key-descriptors	
Title	Teaching4Learning: iNEST Conference session
TAGS	Higher Education System, Active learning, Quality & Innovation in Education
Duration	2 days
Details	
Background	<p>Teaching4Learning @Unipd is the result of constant research carried out in the field of teaching in higher education and in international research groups that propose as their ultimate objective the innovation of university teaching. They aim to do so by promoting learner-centered approach, aligning with the Agenda for the modernization of the European higher education system.</p> <p>The Teaching4Learning @Unipd is an actual plan for the development of teaching and e-learning skills of the teachers at the University of Padua.</p> <p>The teachers voluntarily involved in the project are highly interested and motivated, with a significant driver to share their experience with other colleagues. The final target is to create a faculty learning community, with the aim of being able to support each other in teaching practices.</p>
Description of initiative/project	<p>The International Innovative Teaching Conference, organized by T4L Project of UNIPD, supports a comprehensive change in university education. Learner-centered approaches are requested, implemented in integrated environments for the development of meaningful learning and lifelong skills needed for professions and life. After the pandemic emergency, which highlighted critical issues but also the potential of digital integration, the university education system is now called to re-define its identity and the adequacy of its educational mission, to offer strategic solutions at the curricular, design, methodological- technological, and organizational levels.</p> <p>The Conference intends to provide an opportunity to exchange and share reflections and experiences on some thematics that will be the basis of the working sessions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) theoretical lines and models for implementing the culture of quality in university education, considering people, environments, and teaching at the center of transformative processes; b) educational research and the use of data as a contribution and support for change; c) didactic planning underlying curricular and teaching innovation of Study Courses through the involvement and co-responsibility of all members of the university community also within an international perspective in the framework of the ARQUS alliance for innovative teaching; d) organizational and management models of structures/centers for methodological- technological innovation in teaching and the new profiles of professional skills in a faculty development perspective; e) design and re-design of support spaces, tools, and resources to enable the implementation of integrated learning environments aimed at developing multimedia and multimodal teaching processes
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The participation to T4L Conference of the Education Working Group of iNEST will be promoted in 2024 as well the organization of a Session in 2025, to share challenges and best practice of iNEST Universities and enlarge T4L Community
References	https://www.unipd.it/en/t4l-project
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	No specific requirements

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Carlo Mariconda
Key-descriptors	
Title	Tools for MOOC elaboration: Workshop on innovative LightBoard
TAGS	Lightboard, MOOC, Innovative Training Tools
Duration	2 days
Details	
Background	<p>LightBoard is a fully innovative glass-board allowing the realization of videos where the professor can write facing the students. LightBoard can support the elaboration of empathic, easy-to-make video lectures, with no post-production needed. It has been designed and built as a “fixed” training tool, physically placed in a University Department, which can host professors and teachers during recording of lectures.</p> <p>The lightboard is becoming the standard, at least at Italian level, for recording videos in the training courses offered to young students, to improve their basic knowledge in view to the Admission Test to University. In the last 2 years, the MOOC on Mathematics developed using the Lightboard has been followed by more than 100.000 students from High Schools.</p>
Description of initiative/project	<p>The LightBoard can be managed and used by the teacher alone, without supports from technical staff. The Workshop will present the guidelines for innovative teaching using the Lightboard, followed by training sessions and test video-recording.</p> <p>Preliminary programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - principles of using the LightBoard - practical exercises, with small groups of participants - seminar on MOOC design
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	<p>The Workshop on the LightBoard will be organized by the School of Engineering of Padova University.</p> <p>Pilot sessions for professors of iNEST Universities will be made available.</p>
References	<p>https://www.boardonair.eu/</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9pJdkkEjf3Q</p>
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	No specific requirements

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Luigi Salmaso, Maria Cristina Lavagnolo (tbc)
Key-descriptors	
Title	Mapping gender equality in Ecosystem
TAGS	Gender equality, STEM
Duration	12 months
Details	
Background	<p>Monitoring and analysis of the university community's has made it possible to identify three critical points on which to focus political and financial commitment to equality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the start of university careers, with female students accounting for a significantly higher proportion of students in the humanities and health-related areas, and male students in STEM sectors (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics); • the start of an academic career with the transition from post-doc to RTDa (type "a" fixed-term researcher) and RTDb (type "b" fixed-term researcher), where the paths of women and men diverge further in favour of the latter; • top positions in academic careers, where the incidence of women is significantly lower than that of men, particularly in some subject areas.
Description of initiative/project	iNEST Universities, in the recent years, developed their Gender Equality Plan. The activity is focused, by means of a Research Grant, to elaborate the Gender Equality mapping at Ecosystem level. Activity will be performed in cooperation with Elena Cornaro Centre of Padova University, a structure that promotes teaching and training activities related to gender knowledge. It collects the legacy and the history of organisms and groups that have worked for equal opportunities, gender equality and gender-related research at the University of Padua.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The activity of the Research Grant will be carried out by directly involving Gender Equality offices of Partner Universities.
References	Padova University, Gender Equality Plan 2022-2024
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Anna Comacchio
Key-descriptors	
Title	The Art of Management: Unleashing Creativity and Culture in the iNest ecosystem
TAGS	
Duration	2 days
Details	
Background	The arts have a significant and varied impact on driving innovation, enhancing leadership skills, and enriching organizational culture. Creative thinking and problem-solving are encouraged by the arts. Engaging with artistic expression can inspire workers to approach challenges in new and unique ways, resulting in innovative solutions and product development. Creative thinking is a major driver of innovation, and exposure to the arts can help stimulate this mindset.
Description of initiative/project	An innovative educational event organized at the Venice School of Management that explores how the worlds of art, creativity, and culture intersect with the business world. "The Art of Management" will be a dynamic and insightful seminar designed for business professionals, managers, and entrepreneurs who want to harness the power of the arts to drive innovation, enhance leadership skills, and enrich organizational culture. Renowned experts in management, art, and culture will deliver engaging presentations and lead discussions. Participants will have the opportunity to participate in hands-on activities and workshops that stimulate creativity, enhance cultural awareness, and connect with like-minded professionals, artists, and educators in a vibrant and inspiring setting. An art exhibition, which showcases works that highlight the intersection of art, culture, and business.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art and Business Synergy: Discovery of how art and business can mutually benefit each other, with insights into how art can inspire creativity, problem-solving, and innovation in management practices. • Leadership through Cultural Expression: Exploration of how effective leadership can be enhanced by understanding and incorporating various cultural perspectives and expressions, fostering a more inclusive and diverse workplace. • The Creative Mindset: Learning of how to cultivate a creative mindset among your teams and use artistic techniques to encourage out-of-the-box thinking in business strategy. • Art as a Source of Inspiration: Understanding how exposure to art and cultural experiences can serve as a wellspring of inspiration for decision-makers, helping them make informed and visionary choices. • Case Studies and Success Stories: insights from successful companies that have integrated art and culture into their management strategies and learn from their experiences.
References	<p>Tepper, S. J. (2002). Creative assets and the changing economy. <i>The Journal of Arts Management, Law, and Society</i>, 32(2), 159-168.</p> <p>Byrnes, W. J. (2022). <i>Management and the Arts</i>. Routledge</p> <p>Laužikas, M., & Mokšėckienė, R. (2013). The role of creativity in sustainable business. <i>Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues</i>, 1(1), 10-22.</p>
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Alessandro Cinquegrani
Key-descriptors	
Title	A Literary Exploration of Entrepreneurial Culture in the iNest Ecosystem
TAGS	
Duration	1 day
Details	
Background	Building on the rich literary and entrepreneurial heritage of the iNest ecosystem, the initiative draws from the profound insights of writers and the practical wisdom of successful business leaders. It takes root in merging this diverse perspective to shape a more dynamic and holistic educational experience.
Description of initiative/project	The program will deliver an immersive educational experience that fosters an entrepreneurial mindset among high school and university students. Its ultimate objective is to ignite a passion for innovation and entrepreneurship in young learners, equipping them with the essential skills, mindset, and vision needed to drive positive change within the iNest Ecosystem. Through a captivating blend of literature, business insights, and real-world experiences, participants are empowered to think outside the box and seize opportunities. The program offers a dynamic learning environment, with engaging discussions and interactive sessions that delve into intriguing topics such as the evolving identity of the Veneto region, the complex relationship between culture and the economy, and the ever-changing job market. Writers, scholars, and industry experts lead these enlightening conversations, providing multifaceted perspectives on entrepreneurship and labour. The program spotlights entrepreneurship from two angles: that of the visionary entrepreneur and the dedicated workforce, exploring how businesses, once criticised for altering the landscape, are now recognized as hubs of vitality and opportunity. Sessions feature writers who have expertly documented the triumphs and challenges of the workforce, as well as those with roots in family businesses.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Through iNEST's extensive network and digital platforms, the initiative's achievements will be broadcast to a broad audience, amplifying the impact of our efforts to nurture entrepreneurial culture among high school and university students.
References	Michaelson, C. (2010). Business and/as/of the humanities. <i>Journal of Business Ethics Education</i> , 7, 201. Czarniawska-Joerges, B., & De Monthoux, P. G. (Eds.). (1994). <i>Good novels, better management: Reading organizational realities</i> . Psychology Press. "Value of Hendry, J. (2006). Educating managers for post-bureaucracy: The role of the humanities. <i>Management learning</i> , 37(3), 267-281.
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
INITIATIVE/PILOT PROJECT Key-descriptors	
Title	Summer School on Arts and Artistic Languages as Research Methodology in the Social Sciences
TAGS	
Duration	4 days
Details	
Background	The intellectual background of the Summer School on "Interpreting and Utilizing Arts and Artistic Languages as Research Methodology in the Social Sciences" draws from interdisciplinary approaches, critical theory, postcolonial studies, intersectionality, cultural studies, and ethical considerations. Rooted in a commitment to ethical, inclusive, and socially engaged research, it aims to empower doctoral students with the tools to challenge power structures, decolonize perspectives, and engage in research that not only advances knowledge but also contributes to positive social change.
Description of initiative/project	At the heart of our summer school, the critical studies approach serves as a foundational principle, guiding participants in reimagining the boundaries of research in the social sciences. The school will foster an environment that encourages students to question prevailing power dynamics, both within the arts and within society. This approach prompts them to scrutinize how art can be a potent tool for critiquing and subverting established norms and structures, challenging the status quo to illuminate underlying issues of inequality, discrimination, and injustice. The program also promotes decolonizing perspectives within research. By dismantling colonial legacies in both the arts and social sciences, we aim to foster a more inclusive, equitable, and culturally sensitive approach to knowledge production. This perspective recognizes that traditional paradigms have often marginalized voices and experiences from non-Western cultures, and we actively seek to rectify this imbalance. As students delve into the complexities of using art as a research methodology, they are encouraged to navigate sensitive subjects with care and empathy, ensuring their research respects the dignity and agency of individuals and communities involved. Participants are guided to formulate research questions that challenge conventional paradigms, question assumptions, and seek alternative interpretations. This enables them to contribute to a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the issues they investigate.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	Sharing objectives and results within the multifaceted iNEST ecosystem involves strategies such as publishing research proposals, policy briefs, and industry showcases; engaging with media outlets and communication channels for wider dissemination; and fostering international partnerships and exchange programs. Additionally, the use of the centralized online platform is proposed to serve as a hub for knowledge-sharing and collaboration across the ecosystem, further promoting innovation and positive societal impact.
References	Denzin, N. K. (2000). Aesthetics and the practices of qualitative inquiry. <i>Qualitative inquiry</i> , 6(2), 256-265. Finley, S. (2008). Arts-based research. <i>Handbook of the arts in qualitative research: Perspectives, methodologies, examples, and issues</i> , 71-81. Spencer, S. (2022). <i>Visual research methods in the social sciences: Awakening visions</i> . Taylor & Francis.
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #7	
Reference Person	Elena Claire Ricci
Key-descriptors	
Title	Risk management and innovation in agriculture
TAGS	#risk management #innovation #agriculture #entrepreneurship #EntreComp #risk&law #trainingriskmanagement
Duration	48h
Details	
Background	In agriculture there are still large knowledge gaps in terms of agricultural risk management. Farmers often lack knowledge about effective ways to protect themselves from the continuously evolving risks that they are facing. Insurance operators and other professionals often lack the technical skills to develop adequate tools tailored for agri-food-related firms.
Description of initiative/project	<p>This course targets different types of actors: farmers, insurance operators, and other professionals and entrepreneurs working in the field. The course aims at increasing the knowledge of farmers and professionals about the assessment of the multi-facet risks that they face and will continuously face in the future. The course will also aim to improve their knowledge and understanding of the available tools so that they can more effectively evaluate how they work and if they fit their actual needs. Entrepreneurial competence will be fostered, particularly the ability to cope with uncertainty, ambiguity, and risk, that is essential to making informed decisions.</p> <p>Attention will be given to private and public insurance-related and risk-protection tools, but also to innovation strategies in the light of sustainable development to mitigate or adapt to such risks. The course also aims at increasing the knowledge of professionals that develop/market risk management tools about the specificities of the risks in agriculture, so that they can develop and promote effective options for the agri-food sector.</p> <p>Consistent with the objectives of the course, innovation will be a key driver that will also characterize the teaching aspects.</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	<p>List of most relevant topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to risk management - Climate change risks in agriculture - Innovation for risk mitigation and adaptation - Insurance and other risk management tools - law and risk: insurance contract - law and innovation: innovative business and innovative start-up (Legislative Decree 179/2012, art. 25 ss.) - engaging training to increase knowledge and promote skills in risk management - Entrepreneurial Competences - Legal aspects of risk management - Case studies

References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atlas magazine: Agricultural insurance: products and schemes https://www.atlas-mag.net/en/article/agricultural-insurance-products-and-schemes • Banterle A., Ricci E.C., Cavaliere A. (2018), 'Environmental sustainability and the food system'. In Bremmers H.J. Regulating Food Safety Law in the EU – A Legal-Economic Perspective, Springer. ISBN 978-3-319-77045-1 • Benazzo P., voce Start-up e PMI innovative, in Digesto IV, Disc. priv., Sez. comm., IV ed., Agg. *****, Torino, 2017. • Cubico, S., Favretto, G., Leitão, J., Cantner (Eds.) (2018). Entrepreneurship along the Industry Life Cycle: The changing role of Entrepreneurial Activities and Knowledge Competencies. Switzerland (Cham): Springer • European Council (2018). COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on key competences for lifelong learning https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018H0604(01) • ISMEA website on Risk Management: https://www.ismea.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/12127 • Nizza G., Pontrandolfi A. I fondi mutualistici per la gestione del rischio in agricoltura: quali potenzialità di sviluppo in Italia? Agriregionieuropa anno 7 n°26, Set 2011p. 94 • OECD website on agricultural risk: https://www.oecd.org/agriculture/ministerial/documents/Agricultural%20Risk%20Management%20For%20Resilience.pdf • Regazzoni L., Smart contracts e prodotti autoliquidanti: il contratto di assicurazione, in ambiente e diritto 4/2022. • https://www.ambientediritto.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/SMART-CONTRACTS-E-PRODOTTI-AUTOLIQUIDANTI-IL-CONTRATTO-DI-ASSICURAZIONE._Regazzoni.pdf • Silva R., A. Bevilacqua, Active, Constructive, Interactive... Co-creative! Suggestions for a participative instructional and assessment design (2022), in D. Parmigiani & M.K. Murray, Teaching & Learning for an Inclusive, Interconnected World, Association for Teacher Education in Europe, p. 57-80
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	No specific requirements

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #7	
Reference Person	Elena Claire Ricci
Key-descriptors	
Title	What can I do for Climate Change? Evaluating choices in the agrifood domain to build stakeholder agency
TAGS	#climate change #agri-food #active citizenship #agency #consumer choices #entrepreneurship #EntreComp #sustainability&EUlegalframework #criticalthinking
Duration	20h (possibly to be replicated more than once)
Details	
Background	Individual food-related choices and behaviours are crucial for addressing current societal challenges like climate change. The agri-food system, in particular, has strong connections to all the dimensions of sustainability and different organizational forms of this system can have very different multi-dimensional impacts. Thus, it is important to build citizen/consumer engagement on these topics to promote more conscious choices.
Description of initiative/project	<p>The target of the course are young professionals and students (but also individuals of all ages) that we would like to engage in the topic of climate change and food-related choices. The main aim is to foster agency and deliberation in societally relevant choices, like those related to climate change. The idea is to engage with individuals considering their three-facet roles as citizens, consumers, and (present or future) professionals. Indeed, in all three of these roles they make decisions that can make a difference and become agents of transformational change. The course aims at building individual knowledge about climate change and the differential climate change impacts of different food products, production processes, organizational models, etc. This will promote a critical understanding of the information and claims reported on food labels and on other available sources of information and foster agency. This can also favor the appreciation of actual Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) efforts and Sustainable Business models by firms as opposed to green washing strategies. Attention will be paid to entrepreneurial competence, in particular the ability of recognizing ethical principles and challenges of sustainable development. Consistent with the objectives of the course, innovation will be a key driver that will also characterize the teaching aspects.</p> <p>List of most relevant topics: Introduction to climate change – sustainability, CSR and business in the EU legal framework – Sustainability issues of the food system – Entrepreneurial Competences – Information and mis-information – development of critical thinking – The role of citizens, consumers, and professionals in promoting more climate friendly practices</p>
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Banterle A., Ricci E.C., Cavaliere A. (2018), 'Environmental sustainability and the food system'. In Bremmers H.J. <i>Regulating Food Safety Law in the EU – A Legal-Economic Perspective</i>, Springer. ISBN 978-3-319-77045-1 Cubico, S., Favretto, G., Leitão, J., Cantner (Eds.) (2018). <i>Entrepreneurship along the Industry Life Cycle: The changing role of Entrepreneurial Activities and Knowledge Competencies</i>. Switzerland (Cham): Springer EC (2019), Special Eurobarometer 490, Climate Change. https://ec.europa.eu/commfrontoffice/publicopinion European Council (2018). <i>COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on key competences for lifelong learning</i> https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018H0604(01) Brien, K. and Sygna, L. (2013) <i>Responding to Climate Change: The Three Spheres of Transformation</i>. Proceedings of Transformation in a Changing Climate, 19-21 June 2013, Oslo, Norway. University of Oslo. Silva, R. (2023), <i>Quali esperienze didattiche per promuovere le competenze trasversali</i>, Scientia, vol. 1, n. 1, pp. 141-153, doi: 10.53134/9433-202301-141.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tasquier, G., Knain, E., Jornet, A. (2022). Scientific Literacies for Change Making: Equipping the Young to Tackle Current Societal Challenges. <i>Front. Educ.</i> 7:689329 • United Nations Climate Action website: 'Food and Climate Change: Healthy diets for a healthier planet - https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/science/climate-issues/food
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	No specific requirements

Innovative Education Initiatives & Pilot-Projects	
SPOKE #8	
Reference Person	Donata Vianelli
Key-descriptors	
Title	Summer School in Sustainability and Digitalization in the Blue Economy
TAGS	Sustainability, Digitalization, Blue Economy, Ports, Shipyards, Transport Systems, Logistics, Maritime Industry, Energy.
Duration	35 hours – 1 week
Details	
Background	<i>STEM or Economic Background</i>
Description of initiative/project	The Summer School will focus on how sustainability and digitalization impact the industry involved in blue economy issues. The summer school program will cover problems, impacts and opportunities that ports, shipyards, transport and logistic operators, as well as the maritime industry in general, face from the perspective of digitalization and sustainability. The teaching methodology will include frontal lessons, teamwork, and company visits.
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The Summer School is open to 30 students from all the iNEST Partners interested in deepening the digitalization and sustainability issues in the blue economy context.
References	
Criteria for Participation	
Requirements	<i>Engineering or Economics and Business or Informatics and Data Science Bachelor and Master students.</i>

MISSIONE 4
ISTRUZIONE
RICERCA

Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

Education
& Lifelong Learning

i NEST

Finanziato dall'Unione europea
Next Generation EU

Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca

Italia domani
2021-2027

Milestone #26

Annex 2

*Catalogue
of
Minors
&
Challenges*

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives

SPOKE #1		
Reference Persons	Guido Orzes, Daniele Morselli	
Key-descriptors		
Title	Mountain Innovation Challenge	
TAGS	Design Thinking, Problem Based Learning, Challenge	
Duration	3 days (around 20 hours of activities)	
Details		
Background	<p>In February 2022, the Free University of Bolzano and the NOI Techpark of Bolzano designed and offered an extra-curricular programme for bachelors and masters students entitled “Students & Company Sprint”. Three companies presented an innovation challenge that student teams had to solve, mentored by experts and scientists (following the Google Desing Sprint Methodology). The programme will be re-organized in 2024-2026 thanks to financing from the European Social Fund.</p> <p>Within the iNEST project, the idea is to design a similar challenge but with some peculiarities: (1) the topic will be innovation for mountain areas; (2) the challenges will be proposed by the Spoke 1 of the iNEST consortium rather than by companies; (3) it will be addressed to students from different universities; (4) it will be organized in a weekend formula (3 days).</p>	
Description of initiative/project	<p>The Mountain Innovation Challenge is an extra-curricular programme for bachelors and masters students of the Universities of the iNEST consortium. Students will be divided into interdisciplinary and inter-university groups and work on the solutions of some key challenges on the macro-topic of innovations in mountain areas. They will be coached and mentored by experts of design thinking as well as by thematic experts (professors and researches of the iNEST consortium).</p> <p>The Challenge will be organized at the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano or at a technology park in the region and will last three days (Friday to Sunday).</p> <p>Previous research show that such a programme can have very positive effects on students’ entrepreneurial competences (in particular on the ability to “work with others”), which are crucial for their employability. These effects will be evaluated based on standardized approaches (such as the EntreComp framework). Furthermore, the solutions proposed can then provide a set of interesting ideas that could be exploited by the students themselves or by different actors of the iNEST ecosystem.</p>	
Modality of sharing in the frame of iNEST	The call for students will be spread to students of the 9 universities of the iNEST consortium. The goal/target is to have around 20 students from different universities of the consortium.	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://heinnovate.eu/en/heinnovate-resources/resources/students-company-sprint-extra-curricular-entrepreneurial-week • Morselli, D., & Orzes, G. (2023). Evaluating an interfaculty entrepreneurship program based on challenge-based learning through the EntreComp framework. The International Journal of Management Education, 21(3), 100869. 	
Criteria for Certification		
Requirements	Bachelor and masters students of the universities of the iNEST consortium can participate to the programme (free of charge). A maximum number of students will be set for organizational reasons; however detailed criteria for students selection will be defined.	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Nicola Doppio, Hub Innovazione Trentino
Key-descriptors	
Title	Meditech Challenge – Vascular Surgery
TAGS	
Duration	February 2024 – May 2024
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Requirement for participating to the Challenge as a “solver” is to be a PhD or MSc student affiliated with any department of the University of Trento; or: being a specializing doctor (aka “resident doctor”) in vascular surgery, from whatever institution across Italy.
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The Meditech Challenge – Vascular Surgery is an initiative aimed at accelerating the transfer of scientific and technological knowledge between academia, clinical practice and the medical tech industry. It connects PhD and MSc students affiliated with various departments of the University of Trento with specializing doctors in vascular surgery from across Italy with the aim to tackle the challenges faced by vascular surgeons in their everyday clinical practice. Students and specializing doctors will form multidisciplinary teams that will develop ideas and plans for PoC – Proof of Concept solutions to technological-related challenges pre-selected by a commission of vascular surgeons and university professors, also taking into account insight from the medical tech industry. Topics, knowledge and abilities to be achieved during the Challenge will relate to the: 1) design of customized prostheses (stents) produced with innovative materials and processes such as to allow adaptation to different anatomies; 2) design of smart stents, systems or processes capable of minimizing or preventing the occurrence of type 1 endoleaks; 3) design of systems capable of reducing exposure to X-rays of patient and surgeon during surgery; 4) design of smart stents, systems or processes capable of minimizing or preventing the occurrence of type 2 endoleaks; 5) creation of robots capable of innovating the process and practices of surgical interventions; 6) systems to support the intelligent and optimal planning and execution of surgical interventions.</p> <p>Medical tech companies (large manufacturers of prostheses, stents and devices) will be involved as sponsors.</p> <p>The initiative is co-organized by HIT, DISI – Department of Information Science and Engineering of the University of Trento, and APSS - the Provincial Agency for Health Services of the Autonomous Province of Trento (APSS).</p>
Organization issues	-
Challenge Methodologies	Participants will be involved in activities such as data acquisition; data analysis with advanced software; modeling of phenomena and processes; access to laboratories for the use of machinery; carrying out of experimental tests; field observation; design and engineering of prototypes; reporting and presentations to expert juries, including researchers, vascular surgeons, and leading companies from the medical engineering sector. Teams’ collaboration will be supervised by HIT and mentored by UniTN professors, as well as senior vascular surgeons. Kickoff meeting is scheduled on February 7, 2024; the final event is scheduled on 15 May 2024.
Support documents	Calls for selection of solvers (students and specializing doctors) and sponsoring companies will soon be published on this webpage: https://webmagazine.unitn.it/news/disi/116857/meditech-challenge-chirurgia-vascolare-2023
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	PhD students completing the Challenge will granted a number ECTS (from 3 to 9), depending on the agreements between HIT and the departments of affiliation (DISI, DII, DICAM, Physics). Evaluation methods are being defined along with the staff of the involved departments.

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Ilaria Pertot (UNITN), Milena Bigatto (HIT), Adolfo Villafiorita (Shair.Tech Srl)
Key-descriptors	
Title	Reduce the waste of food served and not eaten in canteens
TAGS	Food, waste, circular economy, consumer
Duration	2 ECTS, from January 2024 to March 2024
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The challenge is suitable for students with background in information technology, engineering, food technologies, socio-economics, psychology, biology, agricultural sciences
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The waste that occurs in canteens is composed by food cooked and not served (potentially reusable) and food cooked, served and not eaten (not reusable for human consumption). There are many reasons for the second category of food waste: behavioral reasons (e.g.: lack of hunger at lunchtime due to the consumption of excessive snacks; refusal to try lesser-known dishes), plates too full of food, wrong portioning and preparing the dish, insufficient time to consume the meal (e.g.: lunch over multiple shifts), etc.</p> <p>The objective of the challenge is to identify new technological and/or educational solutions to reduce the waste of food served and not eaten.</p> <p>Background knowledge: functioning of canteens, legislation, food logistics.</p> <p>Abilities: understanding complex systems (food production, consumption, waste), identifying solutions to a problem by considering various point of view and possible actions, work in a team, prototyping solutions, preparing</p>
Organization issues	The challenge is composed by online meetings and face-to-face activities. In addition, a visit to a canteen in Trento (Risto 3) is foreseen.
Challenge Methodologies	<p>The challenge is divided in the following steps with the related methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of the challenge (meeting with the challenge provider - Shair.Tech Srl) • Background acquisition (logistics, estimation of food waste, function of a canteen, related legislation, existing mitigation actions, etc.) • Brainstorming • Identification of solutions and refinement • Prototyping the solution • Testing with end-users and final refinement • Preparation of the pitch and showcase of the solution. • Preparation and submission of the feasibility report
Support documents	<p>Books: Food Waste at Consumer Level, A Comprehensive Literature Review, Prevention of food waste in restaurants, hotels, canteens and catering</p> <p>Papers: Food waste at school. The environmental and cost impact of a canteen meal</p> <p>Websites: https://www.fao.org/nutrition/capacity-development/food-loss-and-waste/en/, https://shair.tech/, https://www.sprecozero.it/</p>
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	<p>Attendance to at least 75% of the activities.</p> <p>Quality of the pitch and the report (originally, clarity, feasibility).</p>

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Eugenio Aprea, Simone Cerroni, Flavia Gasperi, Ilaria Pertot (UNITN)
Key-descriptors	
Title	Increase the consumption of Mopur (kind of vegetarian meat)
TAGS	Veg, sustainability, vegetable proteins
Duration	2 ECTS, from March 2024 to May 2024
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The challenge is suitable for students with background in information technology, engineering, food technologies, socio-economics, psychology, biology, agricultural sciences
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The consumption of meat is associate to high footprint and carbon emissions. Alternatives to meat are receiving increasing attention by the food industries and the consumers. Mopur is a combination of gluten and legumes fermented with <i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> and <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (lievito madre), herbs and spices, cooked and sliced. It is currently sold in slices resembling animal salami (bresaola veg, salami veg, etc.). The market is considered mature for the introduction of new food preparations that are not presented anymore as salami-like products.</p> <p>The objective of the challenge is to identify new food preparations and marketing messages to address the consumers.</p> <p>Background knowledge: production technology of Mopur, legislation, food logistics, marketing, communication.</p> <p>Abilities: understanding food production (food production, consumption, market), identifying solutions to a problem by considering various point of view and possible actions, work in a team, prototyping solutions, preparing</p>
Organization issues	The challenge is composed by online meetings and face-to-face activities. In addition, a visit to a production plant (Felsineo veg) is foreseen.
Challenge Methodologies	<p>The challenge is divided in the following steps with the related methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of the challenge (meeting with the challenge provider – Felsineo veg) • Background acquisition (production technologies, packaging, communication and marketing, etc.) • Brainstorming • Identification of solutions and refinement • Prototyping the solution • Testing with end-users and final refinement • Preparation of the pitch and showcase of the solution. • Preparation and submission of the feasibility report
Support documents	<p>Books: Meat and Meat Replacements, An Interdisciplinary Assessment of Current Status and Future Directions</p> <p>Papers: Meat substitutes: current status, potential benefits, and remaining challenges, Opportunities for the Adoption of Health-Based Sustainable Dietary Patterns: A Review on Consumer Research of Meat Substitutes</p> <p>Websites: https://shop.felsineoveg.com/mopur/</p>
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	<p>Attendance to at least 75% of the activities.</p> <p>Quality of the pitch and the report (originally, clarity, feasibility).</p>

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Roberto Napoli
Key-descriptors	
Title	SOI-123 Challenge 3: MEC-La magia della pietra a spacco
TAGS	Machines, stone splitting
Duration	October – December 2023
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Students from all disciplines enrolled at the University of Trento, LIUC in Castellanza, or LUM-Libera Università Mediterranea are eligible. Both individual and team applications are accepted. Those who have enthusiasm to share, skills to test, and ambitions to compare are encouraged to apply. Teams are formed based on the criterion of diversity, including field of study, background and experiences.
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	A pure market challenge that MEC, a company known for its commitment to innovation driven by young and brilliant minds, is launching at various Italian universities. Challenge statement: What new technologies (e.g., lasers, connectivity) can be applied to innovate MEC's stone cutting/splitting machines in the next 10 years, and what new technologies (e.g., generative artificial intelligence, virtual configurators, e-commerce channels, virtual assistants) can help MEC communicate the magic of stone splitting to customers and partners (e.g., architects, construction companies, interior designers) in international markets, creating a customer experience (pre and post-sales consulting services) consistent with a boutique of simple and highly functional products, where technology still serves humanity, and the human aspect prevails in the human-machine interaction?
Organization issues	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What business concepts will allow MEC to promote the "magic" of stone splitting to its stakeholders (e.g., customers, architects, construction companies, etc.) with the goal of increasing sales of MEC machinery? 2. How can cutting-edge technologies (e.g., 3D configurators, metaverse, generative artificial intelligence) help MEC differentiate itself from competitors, enhancing its positioning as a "premium" manufacturer (even on platforms like Alibaba.com)? 3. How can MEC develop and offer a superior pre- and post-sales experience compared to the market average, considering that the digital sophistication of buyers is often low? 4. Can it be hypothesized that MEC's customized machinery, where pre-sales consultancy is currently crucial, will only be sold on e-commerce platforms in the future?
Challenge Methodologies	Challenge Based Learning: kick off, mentorships, draft projects evaluations, final presentation to the company team and prize allocation.
Support documents	https://www.mecs.it/en/about-us https://www.soi.unitn.it/courses/soi-123-mec-la-magia-della-pietra-a-spacco/
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	MEC company team evaluates team projects based on feasibility, innovation and creativity level of the proposed ideas.

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti
Key-descriptors	
Title	self-assessment tools for ICT courses
TAGS	
Duration	24 months
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Courses in the information and communications technologies (ICT) sector represent a strategic element for cultural growth in modern society. The same technologies can also be used as a teaching tool thanks to the numerous existing e-learning platforms. In particular, learning can be made more effective through the adoption of self-assessment tools based on remote laboratories and challenges (gamification).
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	This project involves the development of various self-assessment tools as part of courses in the ICT sector such as: Fundamentals of Computer Programming, Data Structures and Algorithms, Logical Networks, Computer Architecture, Operating Systems, Computer Networks.
Organization issues	The budget for a developer is required. Tool specifications and design will be provided internally.
Challenge Methodologies	Self-assessment tools must be developed to cover all the topics of the courses and should be organized in a path of increasing hardness and depth, to provide users a trajectory of continuous learning from the basic knowledge to the more advance strategies.
Support documents	https://elearning.uniud.it/moodle/login/index.php (please send an email to pierluca.montessoro@uniud.it for a guest account)
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	Evaluation questionnaires submitted to students

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti
Key-descriptors	
Title	Video Analysis and Teacher Training
TAGS	
Duration	24 months
Details	
Preliminary requirements	<p>The use of video as a learning tool in teacher education and professional development has increasingly spread over the past decades and has been proposed over time according to different approaches and aims, from being a means to illustrate good teaching practices with a focus on “learning to teach” to being a medium for reflection on action and for the development of teachers’ professional judgment.</p> <p>As shown by existing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of video-based teacher training, video analysis can promote teachers’ ability to identify and focus attention on relevant classroom events, to critically examine and interpret them in connection with their professional knowledge and experience, to question themselves about their beliefs and practices and develop new perspectives for the improvement of their teaching.</p>
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>In line with the developments in teacher training approaches, the most recent literature emphasizes the potential of video analysis in promoting the professional vision of teachers. In particular, by offering the opportunity for a “second-hand” experience of teaching through the immersion in authentic classroom situations captured in their richness and complexity, video analysis can foster the development of noticing and reasoning skills supported by a process of recursive interaction between theory and practice.</p> <p>The project pursues the following aims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Develop a system of methodologies, tools and procedures for video analysis to foster the improvement of the teaching skills of university teachers - Test the system within a pilot training course aimed at UniUD teachers
Organization issues	Video Analysis for quality teaching in Higher Education is a research project promoted by the LID (Dill)
Challenge Methodologies	<p>The training intervention model based on video analysis aimed at university teachers to promote their teaching skills was defined on the basis of the following theoretical and methodological guidelines:</p> <p>adoption of an active and participatory approach in which the expert/trainer takes on the role of "facilitator" to guide and support teachers in the analysis and critical reflection on teaching for the improvement of their practices;</p> <p>in line with this approach, use of video as a "springboard" for analyzing and discussing authentic examples of "ordinary" classroom situations, not for showing “exemplary” or excellent teaching practices;</p>
Support documents	
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	Implementation of the pilot course aimed at SFP (DILL) teachers and evaluation of the effectiveness of the video-based training model proposed through a one-group pre-/post-test design (initial and final assessment to measure the learning outcomes of the course in terms of changes in the beliefs, knowledge and skills of the participating university teachers).

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti
Key-descriptors	
Title	E-Racing Team
TAGS	Formula Student, Electric car, Formula Electric
Duration	48 months
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The project is open to students from the second year onwards of the courses of study offered at the University of Udine (not limited to engineering studies)
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The aims of the project is to provide to the participating student the opportunity to develop a complete engineering project, with the final purpose to design, produce and test an electric competition vehicle to participate to the Formula Students championship.</p> <p>The University of Udine has participated for the first time in 2023 to the Formula Student events held in Italy and Spain. The project will continue the next years with the development of the existing vehicle and with new students involved in the team. By their participation to the projects, the students have the opportunities to empowering their engineering skills and acquire new soft skill that will be surely useful for a faster and smoother entry into their professional life</p>
Organization issues	Mainly the requirement of budget for the construction and development of the vehicle
Challenge Methodologies	<p>The challenge evaluates the team work by static and dynamic events.</p> <p>The static events include the presentation of the business plan, of the cost report and the design event where the project will be analyzed and commented in detail by professional o the automotive world. The dynamic events include the vehicle technical inspection (agreement to the race rules and realization with “good engineering practice”) and performance test in different circuits</p>
Support documents	https://www.formula-ata.it/ https://www.formulastudent.es/
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	<p>The number of students involved with respect of the 2023 edition</p> <p>The total number of CFU delivered to the participating students with respect of the 2023 edition</p>

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti
Key-descriptors	
Title	AeroUD
TAGS	Air Cargo Challenge
Duration	48 months
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The project is open to students from the second year onwards of the courses of study on mechanical, electrical and managerial engineering
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The aims of the project is to provide to the participating student the opportunity to develop a complete engineering project, with the final purpose to design, produce and test o fixed wing drone to participate at the international competition Air Cargo Challenge (ACC)</p> <p>The University of Udine has participated to ACC since 2015 and the team is currently working for the 2024 competition. The ACC is held every second year and organized by the winning team of the previous edition. It sees involved about 40 teams representing universities form all over the Europe, middle east and south Americas. By their participation to the projects, the students have the opportunities to empowering their engineering skills and acquire new soft skill that will be surely useful for a faster and smoother entry into their professional life</p>
Organization issues	Mainly the requirement of budget for the construction and development of the drone
Challenge Methodologies	<p>The challenge evaluates the team work by static and dynamic events.</p> <p>The static events include the presentation of a design report and e technical presentation to be held in public. The team work will be judged by a panel of experts form the aerospace industries. The dynamic events include the Drone technical inspection (agreement to the race rules and realization with “good engineering practice”) and a number of flight mission that changes at every competition edition.</p>
Support documents	https://www.aachen-drone.de/acc-24/ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Air_Cargo_Challenge
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	<p>The number of students involved with respect of the 2022 edition</p> <p>The total number of CFU delivered to the participating students with respect of the 2022 edition</p>

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo
Key-descriptors	
Title	The RAIDMAP experience: training students at design of R&I projects
TAGS	Horizon Europe, Research & Innovation, Technology Readiness Level
Duration	24 hours
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Scientific or technical basic knowledge, Master Degree students
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>RAIDMAP (RAW IDEas for MATerials Projects) is the result of an advanced Education initiative, supported by EIT – Raw Materials. The target is that of training “new” (engineering students) and “old” (professionals) generations at cooperating for the development of innovative ideas for future research projects in various Engineering fields.</p> <p>Students involved in RAIDMAP Project develop the following competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the main issues related to Raw Materials and to their main criticality issues (availability, supply risk, environmental footprint, etc); • Knowledge on the basic structure of a Research Project (structure, work organisation, business plan, budget, evaluation of impacts, etc); • Working in a multidisciplinary and international team with colleagues with different backgrounds and cultural heritage, and with industrial tutors, joined together to develop new “European” ideas in the field of Raw Materials; • Capability of presenting project idea and structure in an international competitive context
Organization issues	1-day Workshop + remote team work + final workshop
Challenge Methodologies	<p>RAIDMAP brings together students and industry through real technological issues, and is based on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting event (1-day), properly designed in order to match students’ fresh ideas with professionals’ experience, approaching existing industrial issues on themes such as circular economy, recyclability and substitution of critical raw materials; • Team work, in which students, remotely coached by professional tutors will develop a project idea, followed by on-line presentations and preliminary selection; <p>Final workshop, in which students will present the up-graded project ideas to a board of experts, to check their potential for becoming real research projects or startups in the frame iNEST Ecosystem</p>
Support documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The RAIDMAP Experience - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J04RZnH_BS4 • https://www.ingegneria.unipd.it/progetti/progetto-raidmap
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	An iNEST committee evaluates team projects based on feasibility, innovation, structure and work/budget organization of project ideas presented in view of RAIDMAP Open Badge assignment

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo
Key-descriptors	
Title	Transitions Technologies
TAGS	
Duration	30 CFU
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Students must have already achieved a Bachelor degree in Engineering
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>Transitions Technologies is a new educational project developed by the School of Engineering that aims to address the multidimensional problems posed by the ecological transition and the digital transition in support of infrastructure. Innovative courses have been developed, integrated with existing master's degree programmes, that have been designed to promote two new interdisciplinary professional roles: the Green Technologies Expert and the Smart Infrastructures Expert.</p> <p>The aim is to train young engineers who are able to operate in a timely and reliable manner within a rapidly-evolving technological environment, through an interdisciplinary approach to problem solving and a systemic view in addition to specific disciplinary training.</p> <p>The Transitions Technologies Project addresses the training of engineering professionals who are able to address the multidimensional problems posed by the ecological transition (the Green Technologies Expert) and by the digital transition in support of infrastructure (the Smart Infrastructures Expert). These topics are of great strategic relevance, both within the framework of the Next Generation EU Programme and within the context of the measures envisaged by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan for transversal skills.</p> <p>The Transitions Technologies programme offers flexible, interdisciplinary courses designed to enrich and enhance curricular activities and to create new professional roles, which are strategically relevant in the changing world of work.</p>
Organization issues	Details and info are available at https://www.ingegneria.unipd.it/en/degree/transitions-technologies/further-information-and-pre-accession-form
Challenge Methodologies	<p>The educational programme for the Green Technologies Expert or the Smart Infrastructures Expert is established and integrated in a Master's degree programme, for a total of 30 educational credits (of which at least 21 educational credits are acquired in "transversal" fields and not in the main fields of the specific Master's degree):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18 or 15 curricular educational credits as part of the minimum 120 educational credits for a Master's degree • 12 or 15 educational credits acquired as extra-curricular credits, in addition to the 120 educational credits required for a Master's degree
Support documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.ingegneria.unipd.it/en/degree/transitions-technologies • https://www.ingegneria.unipd.it/en/degree/transitions-technologies/multimedia-materials
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	The plan is for each Transitions Technologies Project course to be certified through an Open Badge that will digitally attest to the disciplinary knowledge, personal and technical skills acquired by the student. The Open Badge for the Green Technologies Expert or the Smart Infrastructures Expert is different to the one associated with a Master's degree.

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Carlo Mariconda, Sergio Canazza
Key-descriptors	
Title	IA for innovative learning – First edition
TAGS	
Duration	4 hours
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Students must have already achieved a Bachelor degree
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The Challenge aims at stimulating students and teachers at understanding potential and criticalities of AI, in terms of “technological ethics” and “digital rights”, to evaluate real applications, advantages and limits, with the support of national and international experts. The seminar will also face the questions on how assessment and formative objectives might change as a consequence of generative AI. The event will comprise a contest about AI.
Organization issues	Half-a-day seminar
Challenge Methodologies	Seminar, including a contest
Support documents	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rebX86fAbro
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Carlo Mariconda, Sergio Canazza
Key-descriptors	
Title	IA for innovative learning – First edition
TAGS	
Duration	1 day
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Students must have already achieved a Bachelor degree
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The Challenge aims at stimulating students and teachers at understanding potential and criticalities of AI, in terms of “technological ethics” and “digital rights”, to evaluate real applications, advantages and limits, with the support of national and international experts. The seminar will also face the questions on how assessment and formative objectives might change as a consequence of generative AI. The event will comprise a contest about AI.
Organization issues	One-day seminar
Challenge Methodologies	Seminar, including a contest
Support documents	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rebX86fAbro
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives

SPOKE #6		
Reference Person	Monica Calcagno	
Key-descriptors		
Title	Artistic Management	
TAGS		
Duration	2 months	
Details		
Preliminary requirements		
Description of Minor, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The Artistic Management Minor program teaches students how to utilize artistic techniques highly sought after by companies for storytelling purposes. It empowers students with a diverse skill set that bridges artistry and management in the corporate world. Graduates acquire a deep knowledge of artistic techniques for storytelling, cultural awareness, and interdisciplinary skills, making them adept at blending creativity and technical know-how in managerial roles. They gain insights into the strategic value of art in leadership and develop a knack for innovative problem-solving. Furthermore, students hone their abilities in artistic expression across various mediums, narrative development for corporate communication, and fostering cultural competence to excel in diverse environments. They emerge as change catalysts who inspire positive transformation within organizations, all while exploring their emotional and creative potential, cultivating adaptability, and embracing leadership roles that demand a fusion of artistic and managerial acumen.</p>	
Contents of the Minor	<p>The Artistic Management Minor program includes the following specific content areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Artistic Techniques: Exploration and mastery of artistic techniques, including theatre, literature, and video production. Interdisciplinary Skills: Integration of creative and technical knowledge for effective management. Managerial Insight: Understanding the strategic role of art in leadership and decision-making. Innovation & Creativity: Development of innovative thinking and creative problem-solving skills. Narrative Development: Crafting compelling narratives for corporate communication and storytelling. Change Management: Learning to drive positive change within organizations through artistic approaches. 	
Teaching Methodologies	<p>The Artistic Management Minor program employs distinctive teaching methodologies that blend artistic exploration with practical management skills.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interdisciplinary Workshops: The program offers hands-on, interdisciplinary workshops where students engage in practical exercises involving theatre, literature, and video production. These workshops encourage creativity and artistic expression while fostering collaboration and teamwork. 2. Case-Based Learning: Participants analyse real-world cases where artistic techniques have been successfully applied in business settings. They discuss and dissect these cases to understand the strategic use of art in management. 3. Creative Projects: Students work on creative projects, such as creating short films, writing scripts, or organizing theatrical performances. These projects allow them to apply artistic skills and develop narratives that resonate with corporate objectives. 4. Peer Collaboration: Collaborative projects and group discussions are integral to the program, promoting peer learning and diverse perspectives. This mirrors the collaborative nature of artistic and corporate endeavours. 5. Experiential Learning: The program emphasizes learning through doing, encouraging students to apply artistic and management concepts in real-world contexts, ensuring that theoretical knowledge is translated into practical skills. 	

	6. Advisory and Mentoring: Each student is assigned an advisor or mentor from the faculty or industry, providing guidance and support tailored to individual career goals and artistic interests.
References	Sköldberg, U. J., Woodilla, J., & Antal, A. B. (Eds.). (2015). <i>Artistic interventions in organizations: Research, theory and practice</i> . Routledge. Schnugg, C., & Song, B. (2020). An organizational perspective on ArtScience collaboration: Opportunities and challenges of platforms to collaborate with artists. <i>Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity</i> , 6(1), 6. Purg, P., Cacciatore, S., & Gerbec, J. Č. (2023). Establishing ecosystems for disruptive innovation by cross-fertilizing entrepreneurship and the arts. <i>Creative Industries Journal</i> , 16(2), 115-145.
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives

SPOKE #6		
Reference Person	Alessandra Bucossi	
CHALLENGE Key-descriptors		
Title	The Venice Craft and Couture Hackathon	
TAGS		
Duration	4 days	
Details		
Preliminary requirements	Students interested in participating in the Venice Craft and Couture Hackathon should possess a genuine passion for fashion and traditional craftsmanship, an understanding of Venetian cultural heritage, creative thinking and problem-solving abilities, effective teamwork and collaboration skills, research proficiency, adaptability to new crafts and techniques, attention to detail, dedication to the event's objectives, and a willingness to learn and respect the traditions and history of Venetian crafts.	
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The Venice Craft and Couture Hackathon is an educational event that unites the traditions of Venetian craftsmanship with the innovation of a leading Italian fashion brand. Over the course of four days, participants will explore, create, and celebrate the convergence of culture, heritage, and contemporary fashion. Artisans, whose skills have been honed through generations, will unveil their trade secrets. Participants will witness these crafts in action, from the art of Murano glass blowing to the intricate craft of lacemaking and mask crafting. It's not just about technique; it's about understanding the cultural significance that these crafts hold in the heart of Venice. With newfound inspiration and insights, participants return to the hackathon venue, ready to embark on the real challenge. The fashion brand presents its specific objectives and challenges related to incorporating traditional Venetian craft techniques into their designs. In diverse teams formed the previous day, participants brainstorm, ideate, and begin crafting innovative solutions. Workshops and mentorship sessions are held to support these creative endeavours. Experts in both fashion and craft provide guidance to help teams refine their concepts and develop prototypes.	
Organization issues		
Challenge Methodologies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creative Brainstorming: Collaborative idea generation sessions. 2. Hands-On Workshops: Craftsmen lead skill-building workshops / Participants gain practical knowledge for their designs. 3. Mentorship and Expert Guidance: One-on-one and group mentoring from fashion and craft experts. 4. Prototype Development: Teams create and refine prototypes. 5. Judging and Awards: Judges evaluate projects for innovation and sustainability. 6. Networking and Collaboration: Opportunities for networking and future collaborations to promote ongoing innovation in fashion and craftsmanship. 	
Support documents	<p>Gregorin, C., Heyl, N., & Scarabello, G. (2003). <i>Venice Master Artisans</i>. Grafiche Vianello</p> <p>Yelavich, S., & Adams, B. (Eds.). (2014). <i>Design as future-making</i>. Bloomsbury Publishing.</p> <p><i>Manusx Machina: Fashion in an Age of technology</i>. Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2016.</p>	
Criteria for Certification		
Evaluation methods		

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives

SPOKE #6		
Reference Person		
CHALLENGE Key-descriptors		
Title	Sustainable Innovation Hackathon: Transforming the Motorship Concordia	
TAGS		
Duration	4 days	
Details		
Preliminary requirements	Students interested in participating in the challenge should possess a foundational understanding of environmental issues, sustainability principles, and basic knowledge of marine environment. They should be open to interdisciplinary collaboration, adept at exploring cutting-edge technologies, and capable of thinking creatively and innovatively. Effective communication and presentation skills, as well as a passion for sustainability and a commitment to addressing Venice's unique environmental challenges, are crucial.	
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	Rising sea levels, the weight of tourism, and environmental concerns threaten the fragile equilibrium of Venice. Amidst these challenges, a unique opportunity has arisen. The Board of Directors of Actv, the public transportation company, has chosen not to dismantle the motorship Concordia. They see the potential for a sustainable future. The spotlight now turns to a group of university students with a shared passion for innovation and sustainability. Their challenge is to reimagine the motorship Concordia as a floating open laboratory and a symbol of sustainable development for Venice and its cherished lagoon. Stepping aboard the Concordia, participants will find themselves in the company of diverse minds, all driven by a shared purpose: to breathe new life into this iconic vessel and make it a beacon of sustainability and innovation. Teams will form, each dedicated to exploring the boundless possibilities. Envision harnessing cutting-edge technologies, embracing renewable energy sources, and choosing eco-friendly materials to transform the Concordia into an example of sustainable living. The lagoon itself becomes a canvas for creativity, a source of inspiration for ideas that not only rejuvenate the Concordia but also safeguard the fragile ecosystem of Venice's lagoon. Ideas will take shape through immersive workshops and enlightening presentations by experts in sustainability, marine engineering, and environmental conservation. These experiences will equip participants with the knowledge and inspiration needed to craft visionary solutions. The climax of this transformative event is the moment to shine—a presentation before a panel of judges, including industry experts, environmentalists, and visionaries. With passion and innovation, participants will pitch their visions for the Concordia's sustainable future, competing for prizes and, more significantly, the opportunity to leave an indelible mark on Venice and its lagoon.	
Organization issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety and Venue: Ensuring the safety of participants on the Concordia while leveraging its unique venue. • Environmental Impact: Minimizing event-related environmental impact in line with sustainability goals. • Team Formation: Efficiently forming diverse teams with relevant expertise. • Expert Mentoring: Coordinating mentors in sustainability and marine engineering. • Jury Selection: Identifying and scheduling judges with expertise in sustainability. • Technical Infrastructure: Ensuring reliable technical support and infrastructure. • Local Collaboration: Engaging with local authorities and stakeholders. 	
Challenge Methodologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design Thinking: User-centric problem-solving. • Collaborative Teams: Diverse groups for holistic solutions. • Sustainability Assessment: Evaluate environmental, social, and economic impacts. • Prototyping: Rapid development and refinement of ideas. • Expert Workshops: Insights from sustainability experts. • Pitch Development: Craft compelling project narratives. • Cross-disciplinary Learning: Knowledge sharing among participants. • Sustainability Metrics: Establish measurable project sustainability. • Environmental Impact Assessment: Evaluate ecological effects. • Community Engagement: Involve local stakeholders. 	

Support documents	<p>Kasemir, B. (Ed.). (2003). <i>Public participation in sustainability science: a handbook</i>. Cambridge University Press.</p> <p>Karasti, H. (2014, October). Infrastructuring in participatory design. In <i>Proceedings of the 13th Participatory Design Conference: Research Papers-Volume 1</i> (pp. 141-150).</p> <p>Willems, J. J., Molenveld, A., Voorberg, W., & Brinkman, G. (2020). Diverging ambitions and instruments for citizen participation across different stages in green infrastructure projects. <i>Urban Planning</i>, 5(1), 22-32.</p>
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Alessio Cotugno
Key-descriptors	
Title	Revitalizing Cultural Heritage for Sustainable Tourism: The Ippolito Nievo Literary Park Design Challenge
TAGS	
Duration	6 days
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Key preliminary requirements for participation include student status, a genuine interest in literature and culture, commitment to the challenge, adherence to guidelines, a creative mindset, environmental consciousness, and strong communication skills.
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The "Ippolito Nievo Literary Park Design Challenge" is an innovative and intellectually stimulating educational opportunity that transcends traditional learning experiences. This challenge extends an invitation to students, both from high schools and universities, to immerse themselves in a multifaceted exploration of literature, culture, sustainability, and creative design. Students assume the role of cultural heritage custodians and champions of sustainable tourism. They become advocates for the preservation of literary legacies and stewards of eco-friendly travel. This multifaceted challenge is an immersive educational experience that encourages critical thinking, creativity, and a deep sense of responsibility. At its core, this challenge is an avenue for participants to engage in a journey that skillfully bridges the past and the future. It calls upon them to draw inspiration from the literary legacy of Ippolito Nievo, a luminary in Italian literature. Participants are entrusted with the task of conceiving a visionary literary park, one that doesn't merely pay homage to Nievo's literary brilliance but also emerges as a symbol of sustainable cultural tourism. This dual objective requires them to employ innovative thinking, design acumen, and environmental consciousness. The true challenge for students is to craft a literary park that goes beyond the ordinary. It beckons them to envision a space that offers dynamic cultural engagement opportunities. These include not only static displays but also immersive guided tours, educational programs that ignite curiosity, and vibrant cultural events that animate the pages of literature.
Organization issues	The challenge involves various organizational issues, including resource allocation, selection of judges and experts, clear guidelines and criteria, promotion and outreach, logistics and infrastructure, technology, and IT infrastructure, scoring and evaluation, intellectual property and copyright concerns, timeline and deadlines, sustainability practices, crisis management, effective communication and feedback mechanisms, and data privacy and compliance considerations.
Challenge Methodologies	The "Ippolito Nievo Literary Park Design Challenge" utilizes a multifaceted pedagogical approach. It integrates interdisciplinary learning, project-based education, experiential learning, collaboration, and mentorship. Participants critically analyze existing literary parks and focus on cultural engagement and sustainability principles. The challenge fosters presentation and communication skills, all within a reflective and evaluative framework, offering students a comprehensive and dynamic educational experience.
Support documents	"Cultural Heritage and Sustainable Tourism: Challenges and Opportunities" by Xiangyu Wang and Geoffrey Wall (2017). "Teaching for Creativity in the Common Core Classroom" by Ronald A. Beghetto and James C. Kaufman (2014). "Sustainable Cultural Tourism: Small Steps, Big Impacts" by Richard W. Butler (2011).
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE #9	
Reference Persons	Andrea Cangiani, Alberto Maspero, Gianluigi Rozza
Key-descriptors	
Title	School on high-fidelity modelling and simulations for digital twins
TAGS	digital twin deployment, high-fidelity modelling, model complexity, scalability, software engineering, machine learning
Duration	1 week
Details	
Preliminary requirements	This school aimed to research students, early career researchers and practitioners interested in the deployment of high-fidelity modelling for digital twins
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>High-fidelity modelling is core to digital twin deployments when accuracy, precision, and in-depth analysis are critical. However, it poses great challenges starting from model complexity and issues related to computational resources, data handling, real-time requirements, scalability and maintenance. As such, high-fidelity modelling can be the bottleneck for digital twins deployment.</p> <p>This school aims at giving a comprehensive overview of such challenges and propose practical solutions, providing insight knowledge of scientific computing software for the deployment of complexity reduction methods. It is aimed at both practitioners and early career researchers, bringing the most up-to-date techniques to the industry as well as giving mathematical modellers a broader view of the challenges posed by the deployment of digital twins to enhance industrial processes.</p>
Organization issues	
Challenge Methodologies	Complexity reduction techniques such as reduced order modelling and automatic adaptivity in finite element analysis, machine learning, computational science and engineering softwares
Support documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hesthaven, Rozza, and Stamm. <i>Certified reduced basis methods for parametrized partial differential equations</i>, SpringerBriefs in Mathematics, 2016. Cangiani, Dong, Georgoulis, and Houston. <i>hp-version discontinuous Galerkin methods on polygonal and polyhedral meshes</i>, SpringerBriefs in Mathematics, 2017. https://mathlab.sissa.it/cse-software
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	Project for credits (or exam)

Minors, Challenges & Erasmus Initiatives	
SPOKE 9	
Reference Persons	Andrea Cangiani, Rene' Butto
Key-descriptors	
Title	PhD for Innovation
TAGS	Problem solving
Duration	2 days workshop + 3 months challenge
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Participants must be enrolled on a PhD degree.
Description of Challenge, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	PhD for innovation is an initiative of SISSA aimed at PhDs willing to work for a short time on a problem of innovation posed by one of our industrial partners. Students learn soft skills such as time management, the ability to work in groups and to communicate their results to the stakeholders. At the same time, the challenge gives industries and institutions working in research & development the opportunity to innovate by acquiring access to state-of-the-art techniques.
Organization issues	Mini-spring innovation school requires leasing with industrial and institutional partners which will provide the innovation problems. Lease with iNEST institution to advertise initiative song PhD students. Some institutions may need to set up credits to be acquired by participants.
Challenge Methodologies	Based on group work, the methodologies will depend strongly on the problem at hand proposed by the industrial partners. Typical methodologies include data handling and analysis techniques, AI and UQ, deployment of digital twins.
Support documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://valorisation.sissa.it/phd-innovation
Criteria for Certification	
Evaluation methods	Presentation of results, evaluation from stakeholders

MISSIONE 4
ISTRUZIONE
RICERCA

Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

Education
& Lifelong Learning

i NEST

Finanziato dall'Unione europea
Next Generation EU

Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca

Italia Domani
Crescita e Innovazione

Milestone #26

Annex 3

*Preliminary
catalogue of
Lifelong
Learning
Courses*

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli
Key-descriptors	
Title	Challenge based learning: the pedagogy to develop 21st century skills
TAGS	Pedagogy, innovation, challenge, self-directed learning, problem-based learning, 21 st century skills
Details	
Preliminary requirements	This pedagogy can be used at any school level, primary, secondary or tertiary. Hence it is suitable for upper secondary teachers and university instructors. It is a way to conceive the subject beyond knowledge, to develop critical thinking and self-directed learning. It requires a “real world” challenge impacting the community. This is generally given by a social party, a social entrepreneur or a company owner. The students work in groups to find a solution to the challenge and are coached by the instructor; at the end they pitch their solution to the company owner, social entrepreneur the social parties. Most importantly, the role of the teacher switches from the source of knowledge (“the sage on the stage”) to a coach that helps the students in reaching their goals (“a guide on the side”).
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The participants will learn how to design and deliver a complete cycle (or module) of challenge-based learning, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of the challenge and wording - Making the groups of students and techniques for effective groupwork (for example the jigsaw, cooperative learning, etc..) - Timeline with selection of activities to find a solution to the challenge (for example: the problem solving process, ideation, pitching, presenting, the business model canvas, Design thinking techniques, making web searches, etc...); - Use of digital technologies to favor collaboration (shared files, Google Jamboards) - Coaching techniques; - Set the reflection and self-assessment tasks for learning from experience. <p>The competences generally developed in students through challenge-based learning are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - finding an evidence-based solution to a community impacting challenge (problem solving); - working in groups on a challenge (teamwork); - making web searches and find evidence to back a solution (find evidence-based solutions); - pitching/presenting a solution to an authentic audience.
Contents of the course	Overview to challenge based learning – Choosing the challenge and the partners – Organizing the course or module – How to make teamwork effective – The tools for challenge-based learning – Tools for icebreaking and pitching – Design thinking tools – The business model canvas – Coaching the students – Technologies for problem-based learning – Preparing for the finals: pitching – Case studies: examples of challenges from practice – Formative and summative assessment in challenge-based learning
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morselli, D., & Orzes, G. (2023). Evaluating an interfaculty entrepreneurship program based on challenge-based learning through the EntreComp framework. <i>The International Journal of Management Education</i>, 21(3), 100869. • Moallem, M., Hung, W., & Dabbagh, N. (Eds.). (2019). <i>The Wiley handbook of problem-based learning</i>. John Wiley & Sons. • https://kordainstitute.org/ • https://www.encyclopedia.com/education/applied-and-social-sciences-magazines/useful-web-sites-problem-based-learning
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Formative feedback through coaching and self and peer-reflection tasks throughout the course Summative assessment with the final pitches/presentation and assessment rubrics

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Margherita Molinaro
Key-descriptors	
Title	Sustainable supply chain management in mountain areas
TAGS	Supply chain management, Sustainability, Mountain areas
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The course is tailored to post-graduation students and practitioners. There are no constraints on the degree held by the participants, who should however have some basic knowledge on the following concepts: supply chain management (terminology and definitions), sustainability, financial and cost accounting.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>During the lectures and seminars, the participants will acquire an integrated and strategic knowledge of sustainable supply chain management, developing solid managerial skills on how to deal with the main peculiarities and criticalities that characterize the mountain areas. Upon course completion, besides developing an advanced understanding of sustainability and supply chain management concepts, the participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize and evaluate the risks and criticalities that can affect the supply chains located in mountain areas; - evaluate and adopt tools and approaches for sustainable purchasing in mountain areas; - evaluate pros and cons of possible innovative solutions for sustainable logistics in mountain areas; - understand the importance and advantages of sustainability certifications; - conceptually design solutions and approaches for circular economy in mountain areas - understand the principles of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), including the potential and limitations of the method.
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to supply chain management - Supply chain management in the mountain context: peculiarities, criticalities and risks - Sustainability and triple bottom line: introduction and key concepts - Sustainable supply chain: processes and practices - Sustainable purchasing and supplier management: solutions for mountain areas - Sustainable logistics and facilities management: criticalities and solutions for mountain areas - Role of Industry 4.0 technologies for sustainable supply chain management - Company and product sustainability certifications - Circular economy in the mountain context - Introduction to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
Teaching Methodologies	On-line frontal lectures, case studies, seminars
References	
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	<p>Group work presentations and/or written exam aimed at evaluating the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General understanding of the topics - Clarity of answers - Ability to summarize and establish relationships between topics - Ability to transfer the knowledge and methods learned to real practical applications

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Persons	Fabrizio Mazzetto, Andreas Mandler
Key-descriptors	
Title	Introduction to Smart Agriculture Technologies for Mountain Ecosystems
TAGS	Smart Agriculture, Life-Long Learning, Farm Management Information System
Credits	3 ECTS
Details	
Preliminary requirements	No formal requirements exist, but a previous background in agricultural sciences is helpful.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>This introductory course – offered within the life-long learning program of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano <i>Studium Generale</i> – invites interested people to enter to the world of Smart Agriculture (SA) with a special focus on Mountain Innovation Ecosystems. The general definition refers to interconnected and automated technologies to be applied at agri-environmental enterprises (farms, forestry, livestock farming systems) to enable advanced forms of data-driven management decisions.</p> <p>The course will give a general understanding of the SA domain by presenting central concepts, definitions and technologies. Practical applications and needs will even regard mountain contexts, with a focus on extensive farming systems and the needs to identify new full production chains based on niche crops to be entirely carried at mountain farms. Lectures will start with background knowledge on farm mechanization, as well as technologic, economic and site-specific requirements. Common and well-known smart farming applications in crop production, livestock farming, fruit production and agro-forestry will be presented and discussed.</p> <p>Further on, basic components of every SA system will be considered more in detail, with a focus on the following components: sensors, identification systems, positioning systems (GNSS), actuators, hardware and software elements enabling advance decisional application at the enterprises. The way by which all the components will be integrated into a Farm Information Systems (FIS)/ Farm Management Information System (FMIS) will be finally discussed, together with the “decision-oriented” approach (=infologic) to be adopted when designing a new FIS/FMIS.</p> <p>The practical part of the course will focus in detail on the use of the above components (e.g., positioning systems to map entities and land shapes; GIS for managing digital maps importing specific field data; computation strategies for geo-data interpretation to be used in farm management decisions).</p>
Contents of the course	Smart Agriculture, agricultural engineering, data vs. information, farm information systems and related technological component, automation in mountain systems, certification and traceability, new full-chain production models in mountain systems.
Teaching Methodologies	<p>The course is planned as hybrid course, that means only some lectures will be in presence. Up to 50% of the course will consist of online lectures or seminars. A significant part of the course will consist of self-study and independent study using digital sources. More in detail, the course foresees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 hrs front lecture; • ca. 4 hrs online lecture; • 8 hrs exercises at the B5 Agro-Forestry Laboratory and practical field exercises.
References	https://www.unibz.it/it/faculties/further-courses/studium-generale/
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Written test with 30 questions with multiple answers to test knowledge application and skills; possible oral discussion to review wrong answers.

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 1	
Reference Person	Monica Parricchi
Key-descriptors	
Title	Financial education for university students and graduates: build life skills
TAGS	Money, financial education, awareness, future, mountain economic
Details	
Preliminary requirements	No economic or technical requirements are needed
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>Financial literacy combines personal finance, financial concepts, and financial planning to help individuals build wealth and establish long-term stability. Financial literacy is crucial for young adults as they embark on life events involving major expenditure and debt, particularly for university students who are making labour market decisions.</p> <p>Objective: To provide students with comprehensive financial education skills to make informed financial decisions, manage their finances effectively, and plan for their future financial well-being. There will be a series of workshops covering key financial topics. By the end of the module, students should be well-prepared to manage their finances effectively and achieve their financial goals. The course will be organized into 20 hours of blended learning teaching, in presence and synchronous online.</p>
Contents of the course	<p>Three fundamental themes are explored in depth:</p> <p>Introduction to Financial Literacy paying and purchasing; manage personal budget and plan; knowing how to save and how to invest Insurance and Risk Management</p>
Teaching Methodologies	<p>Theoretical lessons balanced with practical applications and real-life scenarios Case study, simulations, group work and role plays</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lusardi, A., Mitchell, O. and Curto, V. (2010) 'Financial literacy among the young', <i>Journal of Consumer Affairs</i>, 44 (2), pp. 358–380. • Lusardi, A. and Tufano, P. (2009) 'Debt literacy, financial experiences, and overindebtedness', NBER Working Paper 14808, National Bureau of Economic Research • Ruspini E., <i>Educare al denaro. Socializzazione economica tra generi e generazioni</i>, FrancoAngeli, Milano 2008. • www.quellocheconta.org
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	<p>Group work presentations and/or written exam aimed at evaluating the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General understanding of the topics - Clarity of answers - Ability to summarize and establish relationships between topics

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli
Key-descriptors	
Title	Curriculum design for university and secondary school's instructors
TAGS	Pedagogy, course design, competence-based education; learning outcomes; assessment, teaching and learning activities.
Details	
Preliminary requirements	This course is for university instructors and secondary school teachers, but also for Young researchers who want to learn the theory and practice of curriculum design. Teaching experience is a plus. Through Biggs' theory of constructive alignment, the course participants will learn how to promote deep learning in their students. The course forecasts workshops and collaborative methodologies, so that participants can learn how to design a course by writing intended learning outcomes, designing appropriate teaching and learning activities - , for example by integrating active pedagogies with digital tools and activities, and devising coherent formative and summative assessment tasks, and assessing learning outcomes against scoring rubrics with criteria and indicators of performance .
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	Upon completion of the course, the participants will learn how to design a module or course constructively aligned, that is with coherent intended learning outcomes, teaching and learning activities and assessment tasks. The participants will also learn to use the most common digital tools to improve engagement and participation (Mentimeter, Padlet, Socrative) as well as cooperation through shared files (Jamboards, Excel, Word). Participants will eventually reflect in written form on the difference between deep and surface learning and how to promote deep learning, thus developing their own scholarship of teaching.
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence development - The theory of constructive alignment - Meet Lisa and Bart, the two prototypical students - Three theories of learning - How much does attention last? - Writing intended learning outcomes - The SOLO taxonomy to promote deep learning - Teaching and learning activities - What really works in education? What evidence based research suggests - Active pedagogies to promote students' engagement and deep learning - How is shaped an effective lecture? Suggestions from evidence based research - Integrating digital tools in the lesson to ensure participation - Formative and summative assessment - Improving the class climate - The power of feedback: the sandwich technique - What is the scholarship of teaching? - Writing aligned scoring rubrics - Writing an aligned module
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biggs, J., Tang, C., & Kennedy, G. (2022). Teaching for Quality Learning at University 5th edition. McGraw-hill education (UK). • https://www.johnbiggs.com.au/academic/constructive-alignment/ • Morselli, D., Ravanelli, F. (2021). L'integrazione tra contesti di apprendimento attraverso le teorie dell'apprendimento costruttivo nella formazione iniziale degli insegnanti. In. G. Cavrini, M. Parricchi, D. Kofler, & M. Cagol (Eds.) Per Tutta la Vita. 144-155. Milano: FrancoAngeli.
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Formative feedback through feedback from the teachers, peer assessment and self reflection tasks throughout the course. Summative assessment with final presentation on a constructively aligned module or course.

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #1	
Reference Person	Daniele Morselli, with partner Universities
Key-descriptors	
Title	Experimental procedure to certify transversal skills to facilitate the transition university to work
TAGS	Competence development, employability skills, sustainability, entrepreneurship, validation, certification, assessment
Details	
Preliminary requirements	<p>Experimental paths for students and young people (also unemployed?) to certify selected transversal skills that can facilitate the school to work transition. These can be for example: employability skills; entrepreneurship competence; sustainability competences very much according to the students' vocation or specialization.</p> <p>Assessment of learning outcome is the process of appraising knowledge, skills and/or competences of an individual against predefined criteria, specifying learning methods and expectations. Assessment is typically followed by validation and certification.</p> <p>Validation of learning outcomes. This is the confirmation by a competent body that learning outcomes (knowledge, skills and/or competences) acquired by an individual in a formal, non-formal or informal setting have been assessed against predefined criteria and are compliant with the requirements of a validation standard. Validation typically leads to certification.</p> <p>Certification of learning outcomes. Process of formally attesting that knowledge, skills and/or competences acquired by an individual have been assessed and validated by a competent body against a predefined standard. Certification results in the issue of a certificate, diploma or title.</p>
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>Certification of competence will be made through assessment or validation.</p> <p>Tools for competence assessment through a problem-solving situation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ an authentic situation, realistic task, simulation according to the selected vocation (this could span for example from 2 to 4 hours to allow for the student's competences expression); ○ During the problem-solving situation above, through specific leading questions, written self-reflection on the situations where the competence has been expressed (to assess how they signify the competence); ○ Interviews or focus groups with the learners on the problem-solving situation and on what the students have learnt (searching for their learning outcomes). <p>Tools for competence validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Analysis of student's portfolio, also to make emerge the competences develop in non-formal and informal contexts (outside school-university) in lifelong learning perspective; ○ interview on portfolio and on the problem-solving situations where the competence has been developed. <p>How competence assessment works: for each experimental path (for example with 25 learners), only a selected number of competences (e.g. 6 to 10) will be certified. The certification is made through the 8 levels of the European Qualification Framework, these describes professional qualifications in terms of knowledge, skills and competences along 8 levels spanning from the upper secondary school (level 4 is school diploma) to second degree (level 6) and doctorate (level 8). When a competence is underdeveloped (example level 2), this is not simply certified.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costa, M. (2011).(A cura di). Il valore della competenza. Pensa Multimedia. • European Commission (2008), The European Qualification Framework for Lifelong Learning , Publication Office of the European Union, Luxembourg City. • Morselli, D., & Ajello, A. (2016). Assessing the sense of initiative and entrepreneurship in vocational students using the European qualification framework. Education+ Training, 58(7/8), 797-814. • Italy: guidelines for the certification of competences. • https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/news/italy-guidelines-certification-competences
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Authentic tasks, simultions, self-reflection, interviews, focus-groups.

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Federico Schena
Key-descriptors	
Title	Facilitate digital integration in healthcare.
TAGS	Extract keywords from the project. Innovation, Change, Digitization, Social and health services, Territorial services, Primary care, Lifestyles, Healthcare/social healthcare professionals
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The training project aims to encourage acquiring skills to maximize the adoption of digital solutions within clinical care practice to accompany the reorganization and reorientation processes of local health and social services. The training activities will take place in a residential summer school and include interactive teaching activities, workshops, and group work supervised by expert teachers.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	Summer School for facilitators of integrating digital solutions is divided into two contexts: a) in the clinical care practice of local health and social services and b) in promoting healthy lifestyles. The courses will be divided into five days for 40 hours and in 4 training modules partly shared (modules 1 and 3) between different groups of professionals and partially addressed to specific areas.
Contents of the course	Module 1 - Technological dynamics in the current healthcare and organizational and digital innovation scenario Module 2a - Co-design of clinical-care processes that can be improved and redesigned with digital solutions also about economic sustainability. Module 3 - Change management models and tools Module 4a - Digital literacy of citizens and patients Module 2 b – the promotion of lifestyles and healthy choices Module 4 b – Use of digital tools to encourage and monitor the adoption of active health behaviors.
Teaching Methodologies	Interactive teaching lessons in a residential form with the presentation of experiences and successful cases of implementation of digital innovation in healthcare with the involvement of both technical-professional components and patients.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schwab K. (2019), La quarta rivoluzione industriale, Franco Angeli • Gjellebæk, C., Svensson, A., Bjørkquist, C., Fladeby, N., Grundén, K. (2020). Management challenges for future digitalization of healthcare services. Futures, 124:102636. • Marques, I.C., Ferreira, J.J. Digital transformation in the area of health: Systematic review of 45 years of evolution. Health Technol, 10:575–586.
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	<i>Evaluation questionnaires for each of the summer school modules and an authentic test will constitute the evaluation of the course.</i>

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 2	
Reference Persons	Anna Serbati, Federica Picasso
Key-descriptors	
Title	MOOC Le competenze valutative digitali/Technology Enhanced Assessment and Feedback skills
TAGS	#Assessment, Feedback, Technology, Digital Competencies
Details	
Preliminary requirements	<i>The Massive Open Online Course is devoted to Italian academics in charge of teaching. A minimum of teaching experience is suggested to attend the course for the best learning experience, considering that the course scaffolds reflection on prior experiences.</i>
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>“Digital Assessment Competences” MOOC is a free and self paced online course, created for University of Trento academics in the context of a doctoral project (cycle XXXVII) with the collaboration of the company Edutech (Trento), specialised in educational technologies. The course is designed in order to foster the development of digital competences in the field of Technology Enhanced Assessment and Feedback practices with the collaboration of University of Trento Teaching and Learning Centre (FormID).</p> <p>The design is framed within the Digital Competence Framework for Educators (DigCompEdu - https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/digcompedu_en, Redecker & Punie, 2017), with specific reference to the Area 4 - Assessment, which divides the assessment and feedback competences of educational experts in this sub-areas and related competences. It is divided in 6 modules: each module is organised with a video, related activities and materials and links to external resources useful for self-directed study. Furthermore, two activities are designed to scaffold reflections and the teaching planning, in the light of the content used during the online course. One-to-one coaching is also planned for university teachers interested in direct experimentation and application in class of assessment and feedback practices enhanced by the use of technology and related tools.</p> <p>So participants are expected to be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Understand key theories and principles in assessment and feedback in Higher Education. -Design teaching, learning and assessment practices through the use of innovative digital tools. -Develop digital competencies related to assessment and feedback strategies. <p>The MOOC could be personalised and extended for Secondary School teachers in the Italian context.</p>
Contents of the course	<p>In detail, “Digital Assessment Competences” MOOC is composed in this way:</p> <p>Introductory Module: introduction to the course with presentation and institutional greetings.</p> <p>Module 0 - Introduction to the new DigCompEdu Educators Competences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -0.1 The DigCompEdu - European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators -0.2 Digital Competence, Evaluation and Feedback <p>Module 1 - The basics of instructional design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1 The basics of instructional design - Part 1. The Expected Learning Outcomes 1.2 The Constructive Alignment 1.3 The basics of instructional design - Part 2. Instructional methodologies and architectures 1.4 The basics of instructional design - Part 3. Assessment <p>Module 2 - The different types of assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Summative/certificative assessment, formative assessment and diagnostic assessment 2.2 Assessment for Learning 2.3 Sustainable Assessment 2.4 Feedback 2.5 Peer review and Peer feedback <p>Module 3 - Assessment and Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1 Technology Enhanced Assessment: the principles 3.2 The value and potential of technology in assessment design (JISC, 2010)

	<p>3.3 Technology Enhanced Assessment systems and the connection with teachers' digital competences</p> <p>3.4 Design examples with Technology Enhanced Assessment (JISC, 2010)</p> <p>Module 4 - Tools for Implementing Technology Enhanced Assessment</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Feedback 2. Quiz 3. Diary 4. Workshop 5. Task 6. Wooclap
Teaching Methodologies	<p>A-synchronous on-line video lectures, with specific practical activities for each module (quiz, reflection activities and 2 design activities in the middle and at the end of the course). The amount of time devoted to watching the videos and to carry out the practical activities will be around 4 hours. In order to sustain the learning process, two online forums are available on the Learning Management System (Moodle), one devoted to peer discussion among academics and one devoted to dialog with the tutor.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Devedzic, V., & Devedzic, M. (2019). Technology-Enhanced Assessment at universities and in schools: An initiative. <i>International Journal of Learning and Teaching</i>, 11(3), p. 89-98. https://doi.org/10.18844/ijlt.v11i3.4319 • JISC (2017). <i>Effective Assessment in a Digital Age. A guide to technology-enhanced assessment and feedback</i>, (2010) http://www.jisc.ac.uk/media/documents/programmes/elearning/digiassass_eada.pdf • Oldfield, A., Broadfoot, P., Sutherland, R., & Timmis, S. (2012). <i>Assessment in a digital age: A research review</i>, University of Bristol, Bristol. • Redecker C., & Punie Y. (2017). <i>Digital Competence of Educators</i>, Edited by Yves Punie. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. • Sweeney T., West D., Groessler A., Haynie A., Higgs B.M., Macaulay J., Mercer-Mapstone L., & Yeo M. (2017). <i>Where's the transformation? Unlocking the potential of technology-enhanced assessment. Teaching and Learning Inquiry</i>, 5(1), pp. 1-16. doi:10.20343/5.1.5. • Tonelli D., Grion V., & Serbati A. (2018). L'efficace interazione fra valutazione e tecnologie: evidenze da una rassegna sistematica della letteratura. <i>Italian Journal of Educational Technology</i>, 26(3), (2018).
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	<p>Full attendance of the modules</p> <p>Participation and completion of all required MOOC's activities</p>

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Person	Carlo Casonato
Key-descriptors	
Title	Digital transition, health and well-being between ethics and technology for sustainable and citizen-friendly innovation
TAGS	Innovation, social innovation, multidimensional evaluation, law, ethics, HTA, value
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Multiple targets differentiated by the type of intervention: Citizens and decision-makers, Master's degree students, Ph.D. students, young researchers, and healthcare professionals
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The tremendous technological, social, and climatic transformations are having and will have an ever more significant impact on society. Managing these phenomena requires updated, adequate, and transversal skills concerning the different social actors (individual, community, business, and decision-maker). A paradigmatic case is the digital transition and its decline to benefit the citizens' health and well-being. Technological innovation is expected to improve the system's capabilities to respond to growing health needs. However, it raises new questions about the accuracy of the cost-benefit ratio and its ethical and legal implications. These issues must become the heritage of professionals (decision-makers, users, and developers) and end users (patients and citizens). The objective of this intervention is to develop multilevel literacy on the topic of the digital transition as an enabling tool for the development of good health.
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Five Seminars open to the population and decision-makers on the topics of Digital transition, health needs, and social impact..; • Ten lessons (10) open to university students with a technological, humanistic, or legal background on the topic of: Value of technological innovation in healthcare and its ethical, legal, and social implications. • Workshop for doctoral students and young researchers on AI in Medicine, state of the art, health expectations, ethics, law
Teaching Methodologies	Interactive lessons with interdisciplinary students; Seminars with experts; workshops: study groups and reporting
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grando A. (2018). Prefazione, in Mavilia, R., & Pisani, R. (2018). Management delle nuove tecnologie per l'inclusione e l'innovazione sociale. Egea. • Tilson, D., Lyytinen, K., and Sørensen, C. (2010). Digital Infrastructures: The Missing IS Research Agenda. Information Systems Research, 21(5): 748-759. • Shaw James A., Donia Joseph (2021). The Sociotechnical Ethics of Digital Health: A Critique and Extension of Approaches From Bioethics. Frontiers in Digital Health, Vol. 3 • URL=https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fdgth.2021.725088 • DOI=10.3389/fdgth.2021.725088 • Lerzynski, G. (2021). Ethical Implications of Digitalization in Healthcare. In: Glauner, P., Plugmann, P., Lerzynski, G. (eds) Digitalization in Healthcare. Future of Business and Finance. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65896-0_14
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #2	
Reference Persons	Giandomenico Nollo, Michele Nicoletti
Key-descriptors	
Title	Converging Frontiers: AI, Healthcare, Ethics, and Law
TAGS	Healthcare, Trustworthy and Human-Centered AI, Law and AI act, Ethics
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Degree in medicine and surgery Degree in nursing-
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The course is aimed at health professionals and gives them the tools to use the various AI systems with awareness and responsibility in prevention, diagnostics, treatment, and monitoring. In this way, the course aims to guide professionals in grasping all of AI's potential and managing and minimizing its risks.</p> <p>After a general introduction to the legal phenomenon and AI techniques, the course focuses on the ethical and legal principles that must inspire a medicine centered on the well-being of the patient and the promotion of their respective rights, starting from those linked to the care relationship. Particular attention is paid to the Artificial Intelligence Act, which will soon be approved at the European level.</p> <p>Depending on the hours available, the topics of data processing and privacy (GDPR) and liability (AI liability directive) may be added.</p> <p>Further editions of the course, of a more interdisciplinary nature, may simultaneously be aimed at health professionals and developers of AI systems.</p>
Contents of the course	<p>Law: introduction to the purposes and similarities of medicine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI: state of the art, definitions and typologies, applications - AI act: <p>Structure and risk-based approach,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Principles and requirements: transparency and explainability, Human oversight, robustness and safety, equality and fairness <p>Data processing, privacy (GDPR)</p> <p>Responsibility (AI liability directive)</p>
Teaching Methodologies	Lectures followed by debate on case studies; learning by doing
References	
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #3	
Reference Person	Gian Luca Foresti
Key-descriptors	
Title	AI-based approaches for Anomaly Detection in Industrial Plants
TAGS	AI for Anomaly Detection
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The project is designed for profiles involved in industrial and professional activities: undergraduates with several years of experience in the companies, senior graduated engineers, managers and, in a lower extent, young graduated engineers.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The aim of the course is to provide to the participating a powerful approach that leverages continuous learning and adaptation to improve the efficiency and accuracy of anomaly detection systems in industrial settings. Anomaly detection is crucial in industrial plants to identify abnormal conditions or behaviors that may indicate equipment malfunctions, safety hazards, or quality control issues. Here's how lifelong learning must be adapted to the problem of anomaly detection in industrial plants: Continuous Data Collection (Participants must be trained to consider that industrial plants generate vast amounts of data from sensors, equipment, and processes), Incremental Model Training (Participants must be trained and informed that data distribution does not remains constant and systems must use incremental learning techniques), Online Learning (Anomaly detection models can be trained online, meaning they update in real-time as new data streams in. This allows them to detect anomalies as soon as they occur, improving response times and reducing the risk of costly downtime.), Human-in-the-Loop (In complex industrial settings, domain experts play a crucial role in anomaly detection. Lifelong learning must incorporate human feedback and expertise).
Contents of the course	Continuous Data Collection Incremental Model Training Online Learning Human-in-the-Loop
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers
References	Amr, T. (2020). <i>Hands-On Machine Learning with scikit-learn and Scientific Python Toolkits: A practical guide to implementing supervised and unsupervised machine learning algorithms in Python</i> . Packt Publishing Ltd Dunning, T., & Friedman, E. (2014). <i>Practical machine learning: a new look at anomaly detection</i> . " O'Reilly Media, Inc.. Pang, G., Shen, C., Cao, L., & Hengel, A. V. D. (2021). Deep learning for anomaly detection: A review. <i>ACM computing surveys (CSUR)</i> , 54(2), 1-38.
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Periodic assessment meetings Final exam

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Applied architectural acoustics
TAGS	Room Acoustic - Reverberation Objective acoustic parameters - Open-source acoustic simulation software
Duration	20 hours of a-synchronous on-line lessons
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Basic knowledge of Mathematics, Physics and 3D cad modelling
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The course will start from the fundamentals of acoustic: the concept of sound and the physical quantities that characterize it will be defined. The theoretical basis will be provided to understand the methods of sound propagation in free fields and in closed environments. Sound-absorbing materials and objects and their application will be described, analyzing manufacturers' technical data sheets.</p> <p>The concepts of reverberation (EDT RT20 RT30) and other objective acoustic parameters (C50 C80 Sti) useful for defining the acoustic characteristics of an environment will be defined.</p> <p>Finally, examples will be carried out in the classroom using open-source acoustic analysis software, applying the theoretical concepts learned.</p>
Contents of the course	<p>List of topics (indicatively, one topic/sub-topic, for each scheduled lecture)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamentals of acoustics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ sound and acoustics ○ acoustic quantities ○ Sound signal analysis ○ psychoacoustic • Room acoustic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ image source method ○ indoor sound-field ○ reverberation time ○ sound absorption ○ Objective acoustic parameters • Case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ in situ acoustic measurements ○ calculation of the acoustic characteristics of closed environments using analytical methods • calculation of the acoustic characteristics of closed environments using analytical methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ description of the calculation software ○ classroom calculation examples • classroom calculation examples
Teaching Methodologies	On-line a-synchronous lectures
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spagnolo R. Acustica. Fondamenti e applicazioni 2015 Utet • Everest F. A. Manuale di acustica. Concetti fondamentali, acustica degli interni 1996 Hoepli – Milano • Egan. D. Architectural Acoustic – 2007 J Ross Pub • Ermann M. Architectural Acoustics Illustrated – 2015 John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey. • I-Simpa - An Open Source software for 3D sound propagation modelling https://i-simpa.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	<i>Evaluation of an individual exercise on a case study performed by the student</i>

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Lighting Design and Assessment
TAGS	Indoor light – lighting parameters – lighting tool and software
Duration	20 hours of a-synchronous on-line lessons
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Basic knowledge of Mathematics, Building Physics and 3D CAD Modelling
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The objective is to understand the many aspects involved in the arrangement of lighting environments and to make informed choices, also considering the different characteristics of the available sources.</p> <p>Starting with the nature and definition of light, the mechanism of vision will be studied, analyzing the response of the visual system to different stresses. Photometric quantities and qualities will be reviewed to describe both light sources and illuminated surfaces. There will be no shortage of aspects involving light sources, natural light and luminaires, in particular LEDs technology.</p> <p>The last notions will have a more applied slant: calculation techniques and criteria for the design of indoor and outdoor lighting will be addressed, considering aspects related to performance and visual comfort and those related to energy saving.</p>
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FUNDAMENTALS OF LIGHTING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature of light. Human eye and light perception, visual and non-visual effects. • PHOTOMETRIC QUANTITIES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Luminous efficiency. Luminous flux. Illuminance. Luminance. • PHOTOMETRIC QUALITIES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Elements of colorimetry. The color of objects. Color and architecture. Color temperature. • CERTIFICATIONS AND STANDARDS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lighting comfort. Veiling, Disability glare, luminance balance. ○ Standards and requirements (EU/Italian regulations). ○ Energy-saving and domotics in lighting. LENI index. • LIGHTING LAMPS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Indoor and outdoor lighting sources and lamps. ○ LEDS. The color perception and power supply of LEDs. • INTERIOR ARCHITECTURAL LIGHTING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Computational and simulation methods and software as a design tool. ○ Indoor lighting strategies against glare. <p>Lighting for commerce and domestic use.</p>
Teaching Methodologies	On-line a-synchronous lectures
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G. Forcolini, Lighting, Hoepli, Milano, 2004 • G. Moncada Lo Giudice, A. de Lieto Vollaro, Illuminotecnica, Masson/ESA, Milano (1993) • Manuale di illuminotecnica (a cura di Marco Frascarolo), Mancosu Editore Roma, 2010 • V.R. Lo Verso, C. Aghemo, Guida alla progettazione dell'illuminazione naturale, AIDI, Torrazzi, Parma, 2003 • M.C. Torricelli, M. Sala, S. Secchi, Daylight. La luce del giorno. Tecnologie e strumenti per la progettazione, Alinea Editrice, Firenze (1995) • M. David Egan, Victor W. Olgyay, Architectural lighting, McGraw-Hill, 2001
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Individual case study developed by students according to standard requirements.

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #4	
Reference Person	Massimiliano Condotta
Key-descriptors	
Title	Spatial information system for spatial planning
TAGS	Gis, remote sensing, geodatabase, special planning
Duration	20 hours of a-synchronous on-line lessons
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Basic computer knowledge
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The scientific content of the course is concerned with the study of theories and processes useful for effectively exploiting, creating, and disseminating geographical information in response to a spatial problem.</p> <p>The course teaches the knowledge and skills to manage data from new ICT technologies to support spatial, urban, and environmental planning processes. The course develops skills and competencies for using big data and Remote Sensing Analysis and evaluating specific analytical methods to extract value and knowledge from them.</p> <p>The urban issues studied will concern environmental sustainability and climate-proof planning. For the two fields of study, the course will focus on defining working processes capable of constituting an innovative and effective cognitive framework for the spatial assessment of the three fields, from which to implement planning solutions and support decision-making.</p>
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New information technologies for spatial planning; • Gis and Giscience; • General principles and tools for database management; • Geographic component in databases (DB) and differences between the cartography and geo-database paradigms; • Vector" and "raster" models; • Principles of modelling reality through spatial databases; • Remote Sensing Analysis and satellite data; • Techniques and tools to produce thematic maps;
Teaching Methodologies	On-line a-synchronous lectures
References	<p>Migliaccio F., Carrion D., Sistemi informativi territoriali. Principi e applicazioni, UTET Università, 2019</p> <p>C. Ratti, La città di domani, Giulio Einaudi Editore, 2017</p> <p>A. Vespignani, L'algoritmo e l'oracolo, il Saggiatore, 2019</p> <p>Balducci A., Mantysalo R. (2013), Urban planning as a trading zone, Springer</p> <p>Vicari Haddock S., Moualart F. (2009), Rigenerare la città, Il Mulino</p>
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Evaluation of an individual exercise on a case study performed by the student

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo
Key-descriptors	
Title	Sustainability & Standards
TAGS	EU Standards, CEN, UNI
Duration	24 hours
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Basic knowledge of Standardization Systems & Rules,
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	
Contents of the course	
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers, Final multiple-choice test
References	
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Evaluation of multiple-choice test performed by the student

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Eleonora Di Maria
Key-descriptors	
Title	Training Modules on LCA & Life Cycle Thinking
TAGS	Life cycle assessment, Life Cycle Thinking, sustainability assessment, circular economy
Duration	24 hours
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The module content requires students to have a basic understanding of environmental sustainability, European policies on the environment, and international standardisation.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The module is organized into 5 sections:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. introduction to LCT and LCA; 2. LCA principles and framework; 3. LCA to support environmental labels; 4. Life Cycle approach for sustainability assessment; 5. LCA for circular economy and for energy transition. <p>Upon completion of the course, the students will acquire knowledge on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life Cycle Thinking approach; • principles and models to evaluate environmental impacts from the life cycle and circular perspective; • international requirements for LCA studies: ISO 14040-14044 standards; • areas of application of LCA studies in the industrial field and its main results; • goal, scope and contents of Life Cycle Costing, Social LCA and Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment; • international and European policies to support environmental impact assessment and life cycle approach.
Contents of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to LCT and LCA: Introduction to Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA); History of LCA and LCT; Need and benefits of an LCT approach for companies; Need and benefits of an LCT approach for the market; Need and benefits of an LCT approach for the public sector; Definition and approaches to sustainability; Examples: 17 Sustainable Development Goals, three pillars of sustainability; European policies related to Sustainability. • LCA principles and framework: ISO standards for LCA: ISO 14040 and ISO 14044; Goal & scope of LCA; Life cycle Inventory and Life Cycle Impact Assessment; Interpretation of results and Critical Review process; Strengths and weaknesses/advantages and disadvantages/ limitations of LCA; • LCA to support Environmental Labels; Carbon footprint (climate change) and Water Footprint (water scarcity); Ecological footprint (land use) and Ecological backpack / backpack (resource consumption); EPD and PEF. • Life Cycle approach for sustainability assessment: Social LCA (S-LCA); Life Cycle Costing (LCC); Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA); Examples of S-LCA, LCC, SLCA • LCA for circular economy and for energy transition: LCA to compare recycling options; LCA to support circular innovation; LCA in renewable energies; LCA to support technology innovation and CE
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers, Final multiple-choice test
References	Hauschild M.Z., Rosenbaum R.K., Olsen S.I. (eds), Life Cycle Assessment. Theory and Practice. Springer, 2018. ISBN 978-3-319-56474-6.
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Evaluation of multiple-choice test performed by the student

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Franco Bonollo, Paolo Ferro
Key-descriptors	
Title	Training Modules on Eco-sustainable Design
TAGS	Eco-design, Circular Economy Design, European sustainable product initiative
Duration	24 hours
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Scientific or technical basic education. Basics of material properties and preferably basic understanding of design process).
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The module introduces to a system understanding of Eco-sustainable design, the concept of a Circular Economy and Design requirements from a systemic perspective as well as a material related design. At the end of the course, the participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand the Circular design concepts, design strategies and how to apply them to individual products; • have an understanding of strategies, methods and tools to implement Eco-sustainable Design; • can prioritize ways to improve the circularity of a product from a systemic life cycle perspective, including materials selection in a CRM scenario; • are aware of CRM related issues with material selection process; • are able to understand the limits of design intervention and indicate potential for the integration of Eco-design strategies in the organization strategy; • have knowledge of various different examples of specific cases.
Contents of the course	<p>Ecodesign and the Circular Economy – Ecodesign in the design process, what skills and focus when? – Ecodesign in EU-Regulation – Circular business models – Product/Service/System-Design - a new leverage for sustainability – A basic introduction to reliability in electronic systems – Energy related design aspects – Deep dive Electronics - Understanding impacts and design – Materials in design and related issues (CRM) – The design process: concept, embodiment, details – A materials selection systematic approach – Co-selection material and shape to serve for material use improved efficiency – How to face multi-objectives design problem in material selection – Eco-design driven material choice</p>
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers, Final multiple-choice test
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EcoDesign Circle (www.ecodesigncircle.eu, www.circulardesign.tools). • Jaeger-Erben, Melanie & Hofmann, Florian & Marwede, Max & Winzer, Janis & Proske, Marina & Wagner, Eduard & Poppe, Erik. (2019). From Take-Make-Dispose to a Circular Society: Introduction of a new vision in six propositions. • Proske, Marina. (2022). How to address obsolescence in LCA studies – Perspectives on product use-time for a smartphone case study. Journal of Cleaner Production. • Shevchenko, Tetiana & Yannou, Bernard & Saidani, Michael & Cluzel, François & Ranjbari, Meisam & Shams Esfandabadi, Zahra & Danko, Yuriy & Leroy, Yann. (2022). Product-level circularity metrics based on the “Closing-Slowing Future-Past” quadrant model. Sustainable Production and Consumption. • P. Ferro, F. Bonollo. Materials selection in a critical raw materials perspective. Materials and Design 177 (2019) 107848. • Ferro P. Raw materials criticalities in material selection & design. Int J Phys Res Appl. 2020; 3: 017-019. DOI: 10.29328/journal.ijpra.1001020. • Sustainable Materials - With Both Eyes Open. • Materials and the Environment. Eco-Informed Material Choice. Michael F. Ashby. Book, Third Edition, 2021, ISBN 978-0-12-821521-0.
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Evaluation of multiple-choice test performed by the student

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #5	
Reference Person	Silvia Gross
Key-descriptors	
Title	Training Modules on Critical Raw Materials
TAGS	Critical Raw Materials, Resources, Recycling, Urban Mining
Duration	24 hours
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Scientific or technical basic education. No further requirements.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The training module aims at introducing the topics of critical raw materials by contextualizing it into the broader framework of natural resources and their scarcity. The module will present the resource topic, along with its regulatory framework, and will then introduce the topic of critical and strategic raw materials along the whole value chain (mining, processing and use, recovery, recycling, End of Life/End of Waste, overall and supply chain). A particular focus will be on mitigation strategy to address criticality (i.e. substitution, recovery, urban mining). A focus on a selection of CRM will be made. Knowledge & abilities to be achieved: recognize and assess CRM and SRM, understanding their technological and economical relevance and the critical issues related to their supply and recovery. Acquire a basic knowledge of main recovery and recycling processes.
Contents of the course	Introduction to resources management – Introduction to Critical and Strategic Raw Materials – Critical Raw Materials act – Relevance of raw materials for strategic technologies – Supply chain of CRM – Mining of CRM and mining charts – Mitigation measures – Urban Mining – Case Study: Rare earth elements – Case study: Lithium – Case study: Copper – Further CRMs – Recovery of CRM: pyro, hydrometallurgical approaches and alternative approaches
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers, Final multiple-choice test
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials_en. • European Commission, COM (2023) 165 final. • Carrara, S., Bobba, S., Blagoeva, D., Alves Dias, P., Cavalli, A., Georgitzikis, K., Grohol, M., Itul, A., Kuzov, T., Latunussa, C., Lyons, L., Malano, G., Maury, T., Prior Arce, Á., Somers, J., Telsnig, T., Veeh, C., Wittmer, D., Black, C., Pennington, D., Christou, M., Supply chain analysis and material demand forecast in strategic technologies and sectors in the EU - A foresight study, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/386650, JRC132889.
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Evaluation of multiple-choice test performed by the student

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
Key-descriptors	
Title	Mentoring creative enterprises in tourist destinations
TAGS	Mentorship, Creative Enterprises, Tourist Destinations, Social Innovation, Sustainability
Duration	
Details	
Preliminary requirements	The program is designed for artisans and craft-makers within the iNest ecosystem committed to social responsibility, entrepreneurship, and sustainability. We seek a diverse group of participants from various backgrounds. To join, craft-makers need to showcase their craft and business goals. They should be open to collaboration, willing to adopt sustainability practices, and actively engage with their local communities. Commitment to entrepreneurship and social innovation is essential.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	The module offers a transformative journey to craft-makers within the iNest ecosystem. The primary aim is to enrich their entrepreneurial acumen while nurturing their sense of social responsibility within the local community. This module is a blend of knowledge acquisition and skill development, focusing on key areas such as social innovation, sustainability, place branding, and tourism. Participants will delve into of craft enterprise fundamentals, from crafting business plans to mastering financial management and conducting market research, craft-makers will gain a solid foundation to thrive. The module will also explore the concept of social innovation and empower participants to identify opportunities for positive social impact within their community. They'll learn to envision their craft as a vehicle for meaningful change. Place branding is another facet of this module that will unlock participants' creativity. Participants will be able to craft compelling narratives and develop strategies to position themselves as cultural treasures within the iNest ecosystem. Tourism integration will expand craft-makers' horizons. Collaborating with tourism boards, they'll seamlessly blend their craft into the local tourism experience, expanding their reach and revenue streams. Community engagement will foster deep connections. Craft-makers will organize events, exhibitions, and cultural exchanges, forging bonds with local communities and nurturing a sense of belonging.
Contents of the course	The comprehensive module unfolds by covering essential craft entrepreneurship topics, emphasizing the creation of robust business plans and financial management. It then delves into social innovation, sustainability in craft production, and crafting unique place identities to position crafts as cultural treasures. The module explores the synergy between crafts and tourism, fostering collaborations with tourism boards, highlighting community engagement and developing soft skills. Real-world success stories inspire, and participants reflect on their impact and chart a path forward. The module concludes with graduation, preparing participants for ongoing mentorship and expanding their craft enterprises in the iNest ecosystem.
Teaching Methodologies	The module employs innovative teaching methodologies that foster active engagement and practical application. Craft-makers participate in experiential learning workshops, collaborate with peers, and analyze real-world case studies from successful craft-makers. Personalized mentorship, field visits, and cultural immersion deepen their understanding of community engagement. Interactive online platforms, gamified elements, and guest speakers provide diverse perspectives, while creative projects and exhibitions encourage hands-on learning and community visibility. Continuous reflection, feedback, and a variety of assessment methods, including presentations and peer evaluations, prioritize practical skills and real-world application, creating a dynamic and inclusive learning experience that equips craft-makers for entrepreneurial success in the iNest ecosystem.
References	Trapp, R. (2015). The creative social enterprise: An impact investment. <i>GIA Reader</i> , 26(2), 26. Naudin, A. (2017). <i>Cultural entrepreneurship: The cultural worker's experience of entrepreneurship</i> . Routledge.

	Tricarico, L., Jones, Z. M., & Daldanise, G. (2022). Platform Spaces: When culture and the arts intersect territorial development and social innovation, a view from the Italian context. <i>Journal of Urban Affairs</i> , 44(4-5), 545-566.
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Enhancing creative thinking with dance
TAGS	Choreography, Creative thinking, Dance skills, Improvisation, Communication
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Embracing the concept of lifelong learning, this course charts a path of reinterpretation with the aim of nurturing essential creative skills needed for career relaunch and professional transitions among aging workers. It promotes actions that facilitate the transfer and blending of skills, with a particular focus on fostering experimentation and cross-pollination processes.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	This course is specifically designed for business managers, with a focus on enhancing their creative thinking skills. Participants will explore various dance skills, including gesture, improvisation, body awareness, and spatial thinking, all of which can be applied to the business context. Through the study of dance techniques, we'll emphasize the creative possibilities that arise from blending different physical practices. Dance is seen as a multidimensional art form, combining music, space, and relationships. We'll focus on the body's role in communication, interaction, and its ability to give abstract thoughts concrete form through improvisation techniques and theoretical concepts. This course offers business managers a unique journey to discover new meanings and interpretations while enhancing their creative thinking abilities.
Contents of the course	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gesture and Expression in Business Communication 2. Improvisation Techniques for Creative Problem Solving 3. Body Awareness and its Impact on Leadership Presence 4. Spatial Thinking for Innovative Strategy Development 5. Creative Cross-Pollination Between Physical Practices 6. Multidimensional Artistry in Business 7. The Role of Music in Enhancing Business Dynamics 8. Leveraging Space and Environment for Business Success 9. Building Stronger Business Relationships through Movement 10. Concretizing Abstract Business Ideas through Improvisation
Teaching Methodologies	Participants will engage in experiential workshops, interdisciplinary explorations, and reflective journaling, encouraging them to draw connections between dance's principles of gesture, body awareness, and spatial thinking and their roles in the corporate world. Through case studies and a final showcase, participants gain practical insights and a deeper understanding of how to apply their newfound creative skills to enhance their effectiveness as business managers.
References	<p>Ropo, A., & Sauer, E. (2008). Dances of leadership: Bridging theory and practice through an aesthetic approach. <i>Journal of Management & Organization</i>, 14(5), 560-572.</p> <p>Zeitner, D., Rowe, N., & Jackson, B. (2016). Embodied and embodied leadership: Experiential learning in dance and leadership education. <i>Organizational Aesthetics</i>, 5(1), 167-187.</p> <p>Biehl, B. (2017). <i>Dance and organization: Integrating dance theory and methods into the study of management</i>. Taylor & Francis.</p>
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #6	
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Enhancing creative thinking with contemporary art
TAGS	Art-Infused Leadership, Creative Problem-Solving, Emotional Intelligence, Interdisciplinary Learning, art-thinking
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Embracing the concept of lifelong learning, this course charts a path of reinterpretation with the aim of nurturing essential creative skills needed for career relaunch and professional transitions among senior business managers and entrepreneurs. It promotes actions that facilitate the transfer and blending of skills, with a particular focus on fostering experimentation and cross-pollination processes.
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	This lifelong educational journey offers a comprehensive blend of creative thinking, critical analysis, and a heightened appreciation for the arts, empowering managers, and entrepreneurs to lead with innovation and inspiration throughout their careers. connections and seeing beyond the surface to unravel deeper meanings. Hands-on engagement with diverse artistic techniques, including drawing and painting, will provide participants with a unique platform to experiment with an inductive approach to thinking. This program immerses participants in the captivating world of artistic expression, where they will deeply understand the synergies between figurative and abstract representation. It empowers them to implement the art of reasoning through metaphors, allegories, and pre-logical mental connections, allowing for a level of strategic thinking that transcends the conventional boundaries of management. These insights provoke fresh perspectives, enriching their understanding of the world and enhancing their decision-making. Beyond knowledge acquisition, this program is a hands-on experience, fostering the development of tangible and invaluable abilities. Through practical engagement with various artistic techniques, participants will cultivate the skill of translating abstract concepts into concrete solutions. This immersive approach not only nurtures an innovative mindset but also equips individuals with the capacity to bring creative thinking to the forefront of problem-solving.
Contents of the course	The course comprises essential components such as foundational understanding of the art-leadership relationship, exploration of figurative and abstract art, creative problem-solving through artistic approaches, consideration of the emotional and aesthetic dimensions in decision-making, in-depth analysis of shared vocabulary between art and management, insights into the art appreciation experience and curatorial practices, practical application of artistic insights in leadership and entrepreneurship, opportunities for reflection and self-exploration, guest lectures from industry experts, a capstone project, community building and networking, and continuous learning resources.
Teaching Methodologies	The teaching methodologies of the course are diverse and engaging, encompassing a blend of theoretical insights, practical experiences, and interactive learning. Participants will engage in lectures and discussions to build a foundational understanding of the subject, complemented by hands-on artistic exploration and creative problem-solving exercises to stimulate innovative thinking. Emotional intelligence and aesthetic dimensions will be nurtured through reflective exercises and group interactions. Reflection and self-exploration will be encouraged throughout, with guest lecturers providing industry insights and diverse perspectives. A capstone project will allow participants to apply their learning to real-world challenges, fostering networking and community building, while continuous learning resources will empower lifelong exploration and growth.
References	Song, B., Formica, P., & Springborg, C. (Eds.). (2020). <i>Business, Open Innovation and Art</i> . MDPI-Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. Sandberg, B. (2021). Art Thinking: Turning an ill-defined phantom into a paradigm for intrapreneurship. In <i>ISPIM Conference Proceedings</i> (pp. 1-15). The International Society for Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM). Sandberg, B. (2020). The artist as innovation muse: Findings from a residence program in the fuzzy front end. <i>Administrative Sciences</i> , 10(4), 88.

Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	

Lifelong Learning Courses											
SPOKE #6											
Reference Person	Fabrizio Panozzo										
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors											
Title	Enhancing creative thinking with theater										
TAGS	Creative thinking, Theatre, Corporate context, Leadership										
Details											
Preliminary requirements	Embracing the concept of lifelong learning, this course charts a path of reinterpretation with the aim of nurturing essential creative skills needed for career relaunch and professional transitions among aging workers. It promotes actions that facilitate the transfer and blending of skills, with a particular focus on fostering experimentation and cross-pollination processes.										
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	This specialized module caters to business managers with a distinct focus on enhancing their creative thinking abilities by immersing them in the world of theatre, a compelling metaphor for the intricacies of corporate life. Throughout the program, participants will embark on a journey through various theatrical skills and concepts, including improvisation, storytelling, body language, spatial awareness, and public speaking, each of which holds profound relevance and applicability within the corporate context. By actively engaging in theatrical exercises and explorations, participants will gain profound insights and innovative strategies that seamlessly translate into the dynamics of the corporate world. These insights will span a broad spectrum of skills, encompassing effective communication, refined team dynamics, heightened adaptability, and innovative problem-solving approaches. This module aims to impart theoretical knowledge and facilitate hands-on experiences, allowing participants to integrate theatre principles into their professional repertoire. As they progress through the course, they will uncover how theatre techniques can serve as valuable tools to enhance leadership qualities, stimulate collaboration, invigorate creative thinking processes, and refine their public speaking acumen, all critical corporate attributes.										
Contents of the course	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>1. Improvisation Skills</td> <td>6. Team Building through Theater</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Business Storytelling</td> <td>7. Creative Problem-Solving</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Non-Verbal Communication</td> <td>8. Conflict Resolution Techniques</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Spatial Problem-Solving</td> <td>9. Empathetic Leadership</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5. Effective Public Speaking</td> <td>10. Adaptability and Change Management</td> </tr> </table>	1. Improvisation Skills	6. Team Building through Theater	2. Business Storytelling	7. Creative Problem-Solving	3. Non-Verbal Communication	8. Conflict Resolution Techniques	4. Spatial Problem-Solving	9. Empathetic Leadership	5. Effective Public Speaking	10. Adaptability and Change Management
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3. Non-Verbal Communication	8. Conflict Resolution Techniques										
4. Spatial Problem-Solving	9. Empathetic Leadership										
5. Effective Public Speaking	10. Adaptability and Change Management										
Teaching Methodologies	The teaching methodologies for this module will incorporate a dynamic blend of experiential learning, interactive workshops, and theoretical instruction. Participants will engage in hands-on theatrical exercises, role-playing scenarios, and improvisation sessions to actively apply and internalize key concepts. These practical experiences will be complemented by in-depth discussions, case studies, and analysis of real-world examples to bridge the gap between theatre and the corporate context.										
References	<p>Riel, J., & Martin, R. L. (2017). <i>Creating great choices: A leader's guide to integrative thinking</i>. Harvard Business Press.</p> <p>Söderlund, J., & Borg, E. (2018). Liminality in management and organization studies: Process, position and place. <i>International Journal of Management Reviews</i>, 20(4), 880-902.</p> <p>Barry, D. (2020). Looking Back on Organizational Theater. <i>Organizational Aesthetics</i>, 9(3), 85-92.</p> <p>Sinha, E., & D'Souza, K. (2022). Experiential learning through applied theatre in corporate training: a qualitative approach. <i>Journal of Management Development</i>, 41(7/8), 431-449.</p>										
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement											
Evaluation methods											

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #7	
Reference Person	Elena Claire Ricci
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Sustainability and Agri-Food: awareness bites
TAGS	#sustainability #agri-food #entrepreneurship #EntreComp #CSR vs sustainability (legal perspective) #sciencecommunication; #edutainment
Details	
Preliminary requirements	<i>No specific preliminary requirements</i>
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>Starting questions: <i>How is it still possible to spread the culture of sustainability in the Agrifood sector? What do we need to improve?</i> A) Technical skills (Agrifood), b) entrepreneurial skills; c) legal skills; d) communication skills</p> <p>a) Module Technical Skills. This module will build a deeper understanding of what is sustainability and sustainable development in general and in the context of the food system, and how business decisions can be analysed and compared from a sustainability perspective.</p> <p>b) Module Entrepreneurship Competence: developing the attention to act upon opportunities and ideas, and to transform them into values for others; based on the abilities as creativity, critical thinking and problem solving, taking initiative and perseverance.</p> <p>c) Module Legal Skills. Knowledge and skills: knowing that there is a European legal framework that is constantly evolving and which companies must take into account to operate in the market.</p> <p>d) Module communication Skills. using tools offered by edutainment and science communication to spread their professional action in an effective and engaging but at the same time scientifically accurate way.</p>
Contents of the course	<p>Technical Skills: sustainable development in the agri-food sector</p> <p>Entrepreneurship Competence: remark and self-awareness on their own strengths and weaknesses</p> <p>Legal Skills: knowledge of the legal basics of sustainability</p> <p>Communication skills: tools of science communication and edutainment</p>
Teaching Methodologies	A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with teachers (total of 20 h, possibly to be replicated more than once)
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bruni F. e R. Silva, (in press) tra edutainment e gamification in Rivoltella P.C. e Rossi, P.G.. (a cura di) <i>Tecnologie per la didattica</i>, Pearson, Milano, pp. X-Y. • Cubico, S., Favretto, G., Leitão, J., Cantner (Eds.) (2018). <i>Entrepreneurship along the Industry Life Cycle: The changing role of Entrepreneurial Activities and Knowledge Competencies</i>. Switzerland (Cham): Springer • European Council (2018). <i>COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on key competences for lifelong learning</i> https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018H0604(01) • Libertini, M. Gestione “sostenibile” delle imprese e limiti alla discrezionalità imprenditoriale, in <i>Contratto e Impresa</i> n. 1/2023, p. 54 ss. • Stranieri, S., Orsi, L., Banterle, A., Ricci, E.C. (2019). Sustainable development and supply chain coordination: the impact of corporate social responsibility rules in the EU food industry, <i>Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management</i> 29(2), 481-491. • UN General Assembly, <i>Transforming our world : the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development</i>, 21 October 2015, A/RES/70/1, available at: https://sdgs.un.org/publications/transforming-our-world-2030-agenda-sustainable-development-17981
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	<i>Online multiple choice test</i>

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE #8	
Reference Person	Alberto Marinò
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Digitalization and Sustainability in the Blue Economy
TAGS	Sustainability, Blue Economy, Energy, Ship & Marine technologies, Digital Twin, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence
Details	
Preliminary requirements	<i>All profiles involved in industrial and professional activities with STEM backgrounds</i>
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<i>The Blue Economy topics will be explored from different points of view, providing knowledge of the state of the arts, mega-trends, tools applied to Blue Economy and Marine systems.</i>
Contents of the course	The length of the course is 24 lectures/hours, articulated in: <i>Engineering and Architecture perspective: 10 lectures</i> <i>Informatics perspective: 6 lectures</i> <i>Life Science perspectives: 6 lectures</i> <i>Economics perspectives: 2 lectures</i>
Teaching Methodologies	Asynchronous on-line lectures
References	Books, papers, websites
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	<i>Final test based on multiple-choice answers</i>

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 9	
Reference Persons	Andrea Cangiani, Stefano Salon, Alberto Maspero
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Digital twins for sustainable economy
TAGS	Digital twin, data-driven modelling, data analytics, artificial intelligence, edge computing, physics-based modelling, physics-based machine learning, system modelling, model order reduction
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Background
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>Digital twins can play a significant role in promoting a sustainable economy by enabling more efficient resource management, optimized processes, and informed decision-making. Their strength is based on bridging the gap between the physical and digital worlds combining various technologies from sensors, data analytics, and artificial intelligence to simulation tools.</p> <p>The course will provide an overview of the tools required to compose a digital twin, covering:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mathematical, numerical, and data-driven modeling 2. Automatic learning for Digital Twins 3. Practical case studies
Contents of the course	<p>List of topics (indicatively, one topic/sub-topic, for each scheduled lecture)</p> <p>Introduction to digital twins. Stages of digital twins deployment. Motivation and typical outcomes.</p> <p>Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning. (UNITS)</p> <p>Data-driven modelling, simulation, and control. (UNITS)</p> <p>Mathematical and Numerical Modelling. (UNIPD, SISSA)</p> <p>Numerical modelling, Finite Element Analysis, Reduced Order Modelling. (SISSA, UNIPD)</p> <p>The course will include in depth case studies demonstrating the use of digital twins in industrial, engineering, and environmental applications.</p>
Teaching Methodologies	<p>A-synchronous on-line lectures, 4 nominal hours a week, 2 synchronous meetings with lecturers/demonstrators.</p> <p>From edition 2 onwards, previous participants will be involved to report their experience.</p>
References	<p>Books, papers, websites</p> <p>Liu et al. Review of digital twin about concepts, technologies, and industrial applications. <i>Journal of Manufacturing Systems</i> 58:B, 346-361, 2021.</p> <p>Brunton & Kutz. <i>Data-Driven Science and Engineering: Machine Learning, Dynamical Systems, and Control</i>. Cambridge University Press, 2022.</p> <p>Hesthaven et al. <i>Certified Reduced Basis Methods for Parametrized Partial Differential Equations</i>. Springer, 2015.</p> <p>A. Thelen et al. A comprehensive review of digital twin – part 1. <i>Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization</i> 65:354, 2022.</p>
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	Group work on a test case. Digital twin proficiency diploma

Lifelong Learning Courses	
SPOKE 9	
Reference Persons	Antonia Larese, Mario Putti
Lifelong learning Course Key-descriptors	
Title	Mixed and stabilised finite element methods
TAGS	Physics-based modelling, high fidelity modeling, CFD, stabilization techniques
Details	
Preliminary requirements	Analysis and Linear Algebra of any degree in Mathematics, Physics, Computer Science and Engineering. An introduction to Functional Analysis
Module description, including Knowledge & abilities to be achieved	<p>The course presents the theory of stabilized mixed formulations for partial differential problems and is aimed at PhD students in computational mathematics, physics and engineering.</p> <p>The instructor is Prof. Ramon Codina, an internationally renowned mathematician and civil engineer famous for his work in computational mechanics, and computational fluid dynamics as well as, precisely, for the definition and development of stabilization techniques for saddle point problems.</p>
Contents of the course	<p>List of topics (indicatively, one topic/sub-topic, for each scheduled lecture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to mixed methods. Some examples: Darcy's problem, Stokes' problem, Maxwell's problem, Elasticity, Reissner-Mindlin plates. Finite element approximation. Matrix structure. • Finite element approximation of mixed problems: general theory. Babuska-Lax-Milgram's theorem. Generalised Cea's lemma. Ladyzhenskaya-Babuška-Brezzi's theorem. de Rham's complex. • Stabilised finite element methods. Basic concept. The variational multi-scale approach. Application to mixed problems. • Darcy's problem. Primal form, dual form. Inf-sup conditions and examples of compatible approximations. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Stokes' problem. Two-field formulation. Three-field formulation. Inf-sup conditions and examples of compatible approximations. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Maxwell's problem. Kikuchi formulation. An example of inf-sup stable approximation. Augmented stabilised finite element approximation. • Elasticity. Stress-displacement formulation. Stress-strain-displacement formulation. Inf-sup conditions. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Reissner-Mindlin plates. Derivation of the problem. Inf-sup conditions and examples of compatible approximations. Stabilised finite element approximation. • Introduction to hybrid methods. Hybridisation of Poisson's problem. Inf-sup conditions. Stabilised finite element approximation
Teaching Methodologies	In presence, a-synchronous on-line lectures, 6 nominal hours a week (3 on Monday and 3 of Tuesday), 4 weeks
References	<p>Books, papers, websites</p> <p>S.C. Brenner and L.R. Scott. The mathematical theory of finite element methods (Springer-Verlag, 1994).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D. Boffi, F. Brezzi and M. Fortin. Mixed Finite Element Methods and Applications (Springer-Verlag, 2013). • A. Ern and J.-L. Guermond. Theory and Practice of Finite Elements (Springer-Verlag, 2004)
Criteria for Micro-credentials achievement	
Evaluation methods	50% homeworks, 50% written exam